

On the Origins of Religions

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ABSTRACT

Analysis of astro-archaeological, plasma/electromagnetic, astronomical, and mythological evidence utilizing [Extended Plasma-Electromagnetic Cosmology \(EPEMC\)](#) hypothesis (a blend of catastrophic -diffusionist-uniformitarianism with Birkeland-Alfven-Peratt plasma, Thornhill Electric Universe, and Velikovskian solar system dynamics) reveals an underlying simplified macrobiotic mytho-historical account of human history. This analysis enables a root-up construction of the origins of religions, science, and the technocracy. Evidence provided includes cross-study comparison of data diverse from plant morphology, optics, geology, cometology, anthropology, geo-archaeology, astronomy, paleontology, plasma and high energy physics, chemistry, and mathematics. Data provided herein is hierarchical, relying upon other works and evidence provided in cross-disciplinary research, amateur and professional, as well as oral histories, testimonies, and historical archaeology. The resultant cosmological analysis provides a satisfactory, simplified solution to the data cited while avoiding impossible pseudoscientific theories for validation (such as dark matter, black holes, ancient aliens, flat earth, man-made global warming, etc...). Conjectures made herein are solely the theories of the author and may or may not reflect the opinions of upstream researchers, either mainstream or alternative, professional or academic. An expanded modern human history timeline is provided utilizing the most current up to date numbers for various epochs of mankind on a global scale utilizing classic, well known cultures as litmus test parameters. The final analysis presents the issues arising from a populace in amnesia and nescience about specific events, and calls out for further research and verification utilizing EPEMC, to see if other hypotheses may be verified or disproved, and for improvements to education and policy making, based upon clarifications provided by such research.

Key words: Peratt Plasma - religion - science - electric universe - electromagnetism - Birkeland Currents - thunderbolts - mound builders - taoism - Egypt - Greece - Nordic - myth - electric geology - expanding Earth - electric arc machining - Moon - megafauna extinction - cataclysm - Venus and Mars - Dreamtime

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Introduction

It should now be *almost* possible to see, with some magnitude of accuracy, and pinpoint (within reason) the various epochs of religious development, in greater brush strokes. It will be impossible with any sort of precision prior to the Buddhist Pali Canon to say how, why, or what specific beliefs were involved except in the case of tablets and stone with glyphs upon them. But with greater cross comparison between movements, and ages of humanity, comparing mythical, astro-archaeological, cataclysmic geological and liturgical evidence it should be quite satisfactory to make some assertions about the origins of animism, shamanism, deism, paganism, monotheism, and the messiah phenomenon. The religification of Science will also be discussed, with examples given.

Finally, a comparison of religious symbolism and analysis of archetypes using Extended Plasma Electromagnetic Cosmology (EPEMC) will be rigorously applied. Startling revelations leads to a call upon researchers to double their efforts in Velikovsky-esque research in order to adjust the direction of mankind.¹

Atalanta Fugiens, Michael Maier

Part 1 - A Diffusionist-Catastrophist Review of Human Chronology

The following tables will make the general assertions clear, before heading into discussion.

Table 1 Epochs of Man (Roughly speaking)

240 kya - 40/36 kya Antiquarian Period	Biologically modern man	Pure animism is expected
36 kya - 12kya Atlantean Period	“Dream Time” aka “Zep Tepi” Origins of language and art Worship of the “Titans” End of Purple Dawn = end of Double Layer plasmasphere around Saturn	Shamanism, cave paintings, crude pyramids slowly refined into Atlantean-esque cultures, especially in Giza area growing in technological prowess; sense of impending Doom
12 kya - 9 kya Tepe Period	Younger Dryas event (Moon or comet) Origins of religious fear of the	Polytheism begins in the form of worshiping planets and animal-gods (Tepe movement); astronomical data

¹ A subsequent study is to be made regarding the full extent of investment in Apocalysm in largest popular media.

	gods; destructions of Atlantis, Lemuria, Sundaland, Doggerland, etc... Dwarka sunk -> Vedas	kept, buried, first distinct astronomical worship cult
9 kya - 5 kya Archaic Period	Age of Destructions and "Clash of the Titans" (Aesir vs Vanir, the triumph of Asgard); origins unknown, possibly the Moon again, possibly early Venus; Terminates suddenly and agriculture resumes in full in Sumer and Egypt, India and China	Cave societies, dolmens, more shamanism, use of entheogenic plants, oracles, sky-reading, sorcery and invoking of spirits for protection and prediction of catastrophe
3500 BCE - 600 BCE Megalithic Period	Dynastic Age - the origins of Nobility and the Priest-Royal dichotomy "War of the gods" End of Saturnian and Jovian age worship, planets begin to diverge; 2 more cataclysms afflict the world Roots of civilization take hold worldwide	Egypt and India create transcendentalism; Death cults, Polytheism, Emergence of comet fear and expectation of war. Origins of technocracy and obsessions of prediction mechanisms Origins of both wisdom traditions AND messiah phenomena (savior planets)
600 BCE - 100 CE Transition or Hellenistic Period	Age of War and End of Paganism	Messiah cults spring up worldwide, driving man towards imperialism and unification of efforts and resources; religions politicize and organize officially Origins of energy schools, wizardry, and chemistry. Use of technocracy now devoted mostly to warfare and in pockets megalithic architecture devoted to gods of the past. This extends Paganism and Animism in the Americas and Asia and Africa by allowing for cathartic remembrance. But it stokes religious strife. Origins of math and math worship
100 CE - 1900s CE Religious Period	Age of Pisces, and of Productivity and Exploration Aftershock comets and eruptions fortify belief systems in pockets of the world Age of Information roots laid down in the origins of Science as research into causative mechanisms for destruction sought.	Separation of natural self and civilized self; religious fervor intensifies in the form of political, social, and technological (even educational) restructuring. Aftershocks generate unusual war and death cults in the Nordic regions, the Americas (especially mesoAmerica), and former Sundaland. There's a movement over time away from ego-centric explanations of the supernatural into mechanistic and principle-driven explanations. Mankind adjusts religiosity and dogma but continues to seek power of the gods. Discontinuing over time the belief in

		wisdom traditions' predictive powers.
1700s CE - Present Scientific Period	Modern Age Age of Information and Science End of feudalistic approach to imperialism Age of Money and Finance (intangible tangibles)	<p>Decreasing reliance on superstition alone, origins of modern energy schools and increasing reliance on empirical evidence to form dogma. Decrease in the power of theism in general; where unable to reduce fervor or adjust it with modern knowledge, continued Age of Warfare.</p> <p>Continued modernized versions of Imperialism and Technocracy comes into full; weapons of the gods begin to be understood and sometimes used upon other humans.</p> <p>Continued, even accelerated obsession with space (the Heavens), and with finding out "who are we" and "where do we come from"</p> <p>Shamanism morphs into alien obsessions.</p> <p>Animism laid to rest or melded with paganism, which falls further behind as most non Monotheistic energy/resource efforts are invested into Scientism.</p> <p>Scientific method begins to degrade as it evolves a blend of dogma with accelerated mathematical worship.</p>

Yggdrasil (left); Kabbalah Tree of Life (right)

The connection of the astrology of the planets, and the religio-energetic and medical systems is not well known outside of occult and marginalized circles of people and academia (such as niche theology). The public generally has amnesia regarding the movement of energy in the cosmos and inside the body.²

² The author's paper regarding Electrical movement and Qi is not yet available. Some discussion has been published here: http://www.academia.edu/8547496/Scalar_Magnetic_Waves_and_Qi_a_first_draft_of_a_hypothesis This work and others in EPEMC supercedes this work and some of its hypotheses are hereby redacted.

Table 2 Cross comparison of the gods³ & titans with astronomy

Planet/oids, Moons & Stars	Sumerian ⁴	Greco-Roman (T/G)	Egyptian ⁵ (OG/NG)	Indian	Chinese	Norse ⁶ (A/V)
Sun (Sol)	Apsu ⁷	Apollo	Harpocrates	Surya ⁸	Yang 陽	Surtur
Moon (Luna) ⁹	Anu Kingu Nanna ¹⁰	Janus Pandora ¹¹ Aphrodite Artemis / Diana ¹²	Khonsu Hathor ¹³	Chhaya ¹⁴ Sanjna Tara	Yin 陰 Chang-e 嫦娥 ¹⁵	Vali Nana?
Deceased moon	Sin ¹⁶	Prometheus	Tefnet / Maat	Soma		Balder
Sky	Anu	Uranus / Caelus	Shu/Tefnut	Vishnu?	Tian 天	Freya
Earth	Tiamat / Ki	Gaia / Hera? ¹⁷	Geb	Prithvi	Nüwa 媧皇	Frigg
Jupiter	Enlil [Marduk]	Zeus Jupiter	Set	Indra Shiva	Fuxi Pangu 盘古	Odin/ Wodan Thor

³ See <https://goo.gl/sQZ3ng> for full table

⁴ Sumerian includes all traditions coming down, such as Akkadian, Semites, etc...

⁵ <http://rickriordan.com/extra/meet-the-egyptian-gods/>

⁶ <http://www.crystalinks.com/norsegods.html>

⁷ http://www.bulgari-istoria-2010.com/Rechnici/Sumerian_Dictionary.pdf

⁸ "When Surya married Sanjna, his wife could not bear the intense light and heat. Therefore, she fled into a forest where she transformed herself into a mare to prevent Surya from recognizing her. But Surya soon discovered Sanjna's refuge. He went to the same forest disguised as a horse. Sanjna gave birth to several children, and eventually reunited with her husband. However, the heat and the light of Surya were so intolerable that Sanjna was always exhausted doing her domestic duties. Finally, Sanjna's father decided to help her and trimmed Surya's body reducing his brightness by an eighth. Thus, Sanjna could more easily live close to her husband." From this we can gather that when the Earth moved closer to the sun, it became too hot, even for our moon. But after some electrical stabilization, we moved into a tolerable orbit 1/8 further away, therefore changing the AU to its present distance. https://www.windows2universe.org/mythology/surya_sun.html

⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_lunar_deities

¹⁰ <http://history-world.org/sumerianwords2.htm>

¹¹ "Hephaestus also created the first woman, Pandora, at the command of Zeus, in retaliation for the various tricks by which the Titan Prometheus had benefited mortal men at the expense of the gods. Pandora was given to the Titan's brother, Epimetheus, as his wife. For her dowry she brought a jar filled with evils from which she removed the lid, thereby afflicting men for the first time with hard work and sickness. Only hope remained inside the jar." From this account of myth it becomes clear that the moon was once part of the Jovian system, as is predicted by its composition and appearance, and was thrown off by Triton/Hephaestus, which was later banished from Mount Olympus (when it became Neptune's servant). This corresponds to the end of Zep Tepi, or the arrival of the moon, when men were lost to Eden/Edin and thereafter to slave under agriculture (Tepe Period forward). <http://www.mythweb.com/gods/hephaestus.html>

¹² "Diana believed her body was very sacred, and so no man was to see her naked. One day a wandering hunter came across Diana bathing. She became very angry, and turned him into a stag" ; the stag is associated with Loki and Loki's horns. This could mean the Awen conjunction and the moon changing Venus' appearance, or it could mean that the myth was re-visioned as Loki is well known to turn from male to female. https://www.windows2universe.org/mythology/Diana_def.html

¹³ The Coffin Texts; Hathor is later in the New Kingdom associated with Venus (Sekhmet), thus the repetition of destruction as associated with a first female fertility goddess, and then destructive warrior princess (true yin vs. false yin).

¹⁴ Literally "shade."

¹⁵ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Chang%27e> Heng-i or Chang-e, floated up to Heaven after Hou Yi shot down the 9 stars

¹⁶ Destruction of the first moon by God appears to be the origin of the fear of "living in sin"

¹⁷ Hera's depiction as Mother evolved, from first being the primeval sun (Saturn), which was replaced as male, to that of Earth, which had thereafter a tenuous relationship with Zeus. It is unclear if Hera is Earth itself, or the life-force. She has cross-depictions with Venus in the Jason/fleece myth, associated with the beard and electromagnetic display/auroras.

Saturn	Ea / Shamash Kaimanu	Cronus	Ra / Re Osiris	Brahma Sani	Shangdi 上帝	Bor / Hymir
Mars	Nurgal/Utu/Marduk	Ares / Mars	Horus	Vishnu Rama	Houyi 后羿 ¹⁸	Tyr ¹⁹ Thor
Venus / Mother Warrior Goddess	Inanna Ishtar	Aphrodite Athena ²⁰ Minerva ²¹	Isis Sekhmet ²² Or Set	Lakshmi	Nüwa 媧皇? ²³	Loki ²⁴ Hel(a)
Titan		Demeter?	Nephthys?			Sif? ²⁵
Asteroid Belt	"Hammered Bracelet"	Argus				Heimdall? ²⁶
Deceased planet	Ninhursag?	Metis	Osiris	Krishna		Hod
Mercury	Gudud	Hermes	Thoth	Rama?	Shuixing 水星	Heimdall/Tyr
Milky Way	Babil Nebo	Rhea	Nu'ut	Dharma	Dao 道	Yggdrasil
Uranus		Pluto / Hades	Anubis			Muspelheim
Ariel ²⁷		Persephone				

¹⁸ "Chinese people believed that there existed ten suns that appeared in turn in the sky during the Chinese ten-day week. Each day the ten suns would travel with their mother, the goddess Xi He, to the Valley of the Light in the East. There, Xi He would wash her children in the lake and put them in the branches of an enormous mulberry tree called fu-sang. From the tree, only one sun would move off into the sky for a journey of one day, to reach the mount Yen-Tzu in the Far West.

Tired of this routine, the ten suns decided to appear all together. The combined heat made the [life](#) on the Earth unbearable. To prevent the destruction of the [Earth](#), the emperor Yao asked Di Jun, the father of the ten suns, to persuade his children to appear one at a time. They would not listen to him, so Di Jun sent the archer, Yi, armed with a magic bow and ten arrows to frighten the disobedient suns. However, Yi shot nine suns, only the [Sun](#) that we see today remained in the sky. Di Jun was so angry for the death of nine of his children that he condemned Yi to live as an ordinary mortal in the earth."

From this we can see that the Chinese remember a time when there were 10 *highly* visible bodies in the sky during the reign of emperor Yao (Yahweh, Ywahoo - the world sound heard from crustal bending), pre Shang Dynasty, or Sumerian times. **1) Sun, 2) Moon, 3) Mercury, 4) Mars, 5) Jupiter, 6) Venus, 7) Saturn, 8) Callisto, 9) Io, and 10) Ganymede.** It is doubtful Europa would have been considered large enough. However, any one of the bodies could be switched. Please note that by this time, Uranus and Neptune (and Triton) would certainly be too far away, as would any Saturnian moon.

https://www.windows2universe.org/mythology/ten_chinese_suns.html

¹⁹ Tyr's "hand" was bitten off by Fenrir; he will get his revenge against Garm (giant dog) at the next Ragnarok. Is this an astronomical prediction?

²⁰ Athena's associated animal is the owl, due to Peratte formation, see Appendix B

²¹ "Following the Greek myths around Athena, she was born of Metis, who had been swallowed by Jupiter, and burst from her father's head, fully armed and clad in armor.^[2] After impregnating the titaness Metis notably forcefully which resulted in her attempting to change shape or shapeshift to escape him, Jupiter recalled the prophecy that his own child would overthrow him as he had Saturn and in turn, Saturn had Caelus." <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Caelus>

²² "A New Kingdom religious composition records rebellion against Ra, prompting him to withdraw to the sky. This 'Tale of the Heavenly Cow' includes the story of Ra sending his eye out from his body, so as a separate offshoot, a 'daughter', to punish mankind. As Sekhmet (meaning 'the mighty goddess') she almost annihilates mankind; the gods trick her into becoming sweetly drunk, by colouring a lake of beer red to look like human blood - she reverts to her sweet character as the loving and maternal Hathor."

<http://www.ucl.ac.uk/museums-static/digitalegypt/religion/deitiescreation.html>

²³ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/N%C3%BCwa>

²⁴ Loki is the "father" of three monsters: Fenrir, Hela, and Jormungand; a mother to Sleipnir, the 8 legged horse.

²⁵ The little known fertility goddess could have remembered from the age of Saturnian orbit in the Tepe period.

²⁶ Argus having "100 eyes" and Heimdall's power of sight could be any of the highly cratered bodies, including Ganymede, Mercury, or Mars.

²⁷ Assumption that only the brightest moon would be visible at all to ancient Greeks and Romans.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Moons_of_Uranus#Large_moons

Great Comet		Nemesis/Venus	Apep	Lakshmi		
Comet tail / Snake		Typhon		Naga	Hundun 混沌	Jormungand
Neptune	Enki	Poseidon Theseus? ²⁸				Ymir (Nep?)
Thunderbolt (EMF)		Pluvius <i>Habeant</i> ²⁹	Bast ³⁰	Trishula Damaru ³¹	Leidian 雷电	Mjollnir
Dipper/ Great Bear		Callisto		Saptarshi ³²	Pih Tow ³³ Doumu 斗母	
Thunderbirds			Horus	Garuda		
Savior Mars	Gilgamesh	Hercules	Babi	Hanuman	Sun Wukong	Thor
Traitor Mars		Mars Ultor ³⁴	Set	Kali		
Io		Io ³⁵				Sif?
Callisto		Callisto ³⁶				

²⁸ Poseidon's changeable character is likely due to the blue planet's wandering nature. The continued worship of the seas, despite becoming further from Neptune (and Saturn), was continued through his progeny. The myths, over time, became vastly more centered around humanity's efforts to survive. Neptune was often invoked as a friend to humanity as well. The "steed" aspect is also referenced in India and Norse, and probably related to a zodiac or plasma shape which changed shape often. This shape may still exist in dark mode, even if the voltage is too small to brighten it nowadays. These shapes may yet return, and be associated with the zodiacs (housing) if, upon leaving the galactic dust blocking our circuit, the [Milky Way's plasma streams reach our outer solar system](#) and [recharge the outer gas giants](#).

²⁹ Pliny, <https://www.varchive.org/itb/thunder.htm>

³⁰ Perhaps one of the greatest mysteries of ancient Egyptian religion was the worship of cats. However, research shows that Bast was "like a knife" and his symbol was that of the knife, still a ritualistic ornament in worldwide magical practices. The knife is best symbolized in the Tibetan [Vajrakila or Phurba](#); itself a probable derivative of Kali, goddess of destruction. Bast is therefore associated with electromagnetism. Given the widespread use of the most ancient/Atlantean Period Egyptian "gods" of this mysterious power, the cat therefore symbolised that mysterious power. Their mercurial natures and occasional heterochromia (two different colored eyes) only heightened that mystery and possibly alluded to duality

³¹ "the damru is known as the instrument of the deity Shiva, and is said to be created by Shiva to produce spiritual sounds by which the whole universe has been created and regulated." The double bell shape is that noted by David LePoint and is electromagnetic.

³² <http://www.seasky.org/constellations/constellation-ursa-major.html>

³³ <https://heathenchinese.wordpress.com/2013/09/08/the-big-dipper/> <http://idp.bl.uk/4DCGI/education/astronomy/sky.html>

³⁴ "Mars Ultor, was among the gods who received sacrifices from Julian, the only emperor to reject Christianity after the conversion of Constantine I. In 363 AD, in preparation for the Siege of Ctesiphon, Julian sacrificed **ten "very fine" bulls** to Mars Ultor."

³⁵ "To free Io, Zeus sent his son Mercury to sing and tell boring stories to make Argus sleep with all his eyes. [Mercury](#) told so many stories that finally Argus closed all his hundred eyes. Only then did Mercury kill Argus and untie Io who ran home free. Yet when Hera discovered what had occurred, she was so furious that she sent a vicious gadfly to sting the cow forever. Meanwhile, Io who was still prisoner into the shape of a cow could not get rid of the malicious gadfly. Finally, after Zeus vowed to no longer pursue his beloved Io, Hera released Io from her inhuman prison, and Io settled in Egypt, becoming the first queen of Egypt." <https://www.windows2universe.org/mythology/planets/Jupiter/Io.html>

This cow is of course related to the cow cult of the Near East. However the "stings" clearly relate to Io's electrical nature.

³⁶ As a "favorite companion" of Diana, this would suggest that Venus was, for a time, in tidal lock with a Jovian moon.

Table 3 Cultural Phase and Architecture comparison chart (with dates of flourishing)³⁷

³⁷ Some dates have been modified based on EPEMC evidence. Others follow standard dating, especially the later periods. The start of a Period does not mean, necessarily, that it was built up. There is no known date to start Atlantean peoples, of all fallen continents, therefore the start date is assumed to be Modern man (language plus brain size).

Speaking in terms of unity, or approaching unity (for nowhere in the world has all of humanity dealt with catastrophe in exactly the same way³⁸) one must of course try to eliminate side-paths and distractive comparisons which may, ultimately be unfair to one culture or another.³⁹ It is already natural to say that objective comparisons cannot be made, given the vast difference of religious behaviors and belief systems (even within small regions and localities). In truth, all of this exercise smacks of Western [white washed], postmodernist analysis and possibly judgment penetrates the analysis. However, subjective observations do render some merit or truth, given the perspective of time and history (itself a slippery slope). Thus it is that the overriding objection to the exercise is itself over-ridden by the driving need of a unified humanity to take a global, objective perspective in reviewing our collective past and making plans for our collective future.

As one can see from reviewing Table 1, there is a clear stimulus-response relationship humanity has with nature and the supernatural (as subjectively experienced), that tends in the direction of: development, prediction analysis, religious adaptation phases, organization and restructuring of societies, and the gathering of knowledge and intelligence. In fact, if intelligence were viewed as a collective accumulation of data about the environment, mankind has, for six thousand years at the minimum embarked upon drastic intelligence gathering and restructuring campaigns as a form of survival that clearly was not deemed necessary for the first hundreds of thousands to millions of years. It can be said that biologically modern humans were perfectly adapted for typical natural survival (mating, shelter, hunting and gathering, socialization, etc...). From a consciousness and religious perspective, such humans, intelligent as we (in potential) would have naturally felt, nestled in the bosom of Mother Nature (Mother Goddess or Gaia) and protected under the watchfulness of Father Sky (God, Uranus). There would have been no question of the supernatural's place or our own, and no impetus to alter this relationship.

The proposed first adaptation seems to have been once mankind began to enter into caves for shamanistic trances and early animistic or occult practices, such as the consumption of psychedelic and entheogenic plants. It is at this point, in places like Lascaux, Chauvet, and El Castillo we begin to see the formations of language, religion (as some form of occult animistic practice), and society.

There must have been some other impetus for the first early pyramid construction phases. While the public favors supernatural explanations such as God, giants/Nephilim, or aliens, the author proposes a more interesting suggestion. At this time, Earth would have been still within the plasma sheath of Cronus (planet Saturn), and generally speaking "Father Sky" would have prevented the visibility of the majority of the pantheon of moons around the then brown-dwarf protostar Saturn (hereafter called Helios, Atum-Ra or simply Ra). At this stage, aside from a soft glow of heat given off, that would have been bolstered by the far distant radiation supplied by a small main sequence star on approach and a hidden Jovian brown dwarf which electrically shared energy with the brown dwarf Ra, and there would (as reported in myth) have been no major seasons, only a constant range of seasons. However, from time to time as moons, such as planet Mars, approached the host star or each other, plasma formations would emerge, as indicated in Peratt⁴⁰ and Talbott⁴¹

³⁸ In fact even calendrical changes, as uniform as they were, came in wildly varied times historically, and when the Earth changed course again, the decisions about further adjustments were not made uniformly everywhere until the Age of Exploration and British Empire's standards conquered the world in the late 1800s.

³⁹ For example, Table 3 makes use of commonly known megalithic cultures, but of course cannot comprehensively display all the known megalithic cultures of the world and the phases within each. The point is to demonstrate how much time elapses, providing ample time for development. Take for instance what is known about Hopewell building. That was a long time, but overall, its period was relatively miniscule. The same thing may be said of the Inca and Aztec. This time compression issue is what generates confusing OOPArts as well as prevents understanding of human development. In other words, because researchers cannot fit it all in the gaps (like the periodic table), it actually opens up areas for superstition (such as aliens), and various misapplications of religious myth and architectural theory. However, by expanding the timeline, it is easy to demonstrate how much **must be missing** and as yet to be found.

⁴⁰ <https://goo.gl/ko1NZK>

⁴¹ [Symbols of an Alien Sky https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=t7EAlTcZFwY](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=t7EAlTcZFwY)

. One of these could have been the fabled “Mountain”⁴² which is actually a 3D plasma streamer from a round source (some planetoid) forced into a 2D perspective from the vantage of Earth. Bear in mind, at the time this first change would have occurred, there could have been some anomalous change in the (then) solar system as humanity knew it. There may have been a first cataclysm to cause early mankind to enter into caves deeply, or simply a growing instability in the elliptical orbits of Ra’s moons as Sol (eventually: Apollo) approached the solar system.

This postulated early event would have provided the impetus of change both socially and spiritually. Ultimately mankind’s behavior would have been drastically changed. It is proposed that the early passing and entrapment of the binary Saturnian-Jovian solar system would have “wobbled” first, before splitting the bond, as the two dwarf stars struggled against the growing electro-gravitational power of Sol. This star may have even been somewhat visible through the plasma sheath. It surely could have driven the changes in our solar system that led to alternations of both axis and orbital distances, leading to Ice Ages (plural). The far off distances of the orbit would have both shrank and intensified into a forced “transition period” before settling into our relatively modern orbits.

It would be good to remember, in our hypothetical exploration, that many hundreds or even thousands of years could have passed without change, and generations of lives would have been spent in continuing the pattern of survival and social behaviors. It would have been by oral tradition alone if any remembrance could be uttered, and there would be no impetus for an educational or institutional program in all that time, until the sky changed completely, and the pantheon of titans and spirits (plasma formations and auroral interactions in the ionosphere) became wholly visible in the sky.

It may be necessary, for a moment, to speak of the effects of the Plasma-electromagnetic effects which would be expected. Firstly, as $e=mc^2$ whenever the charge density in the solar system environment changed, so would all the gravitational effects. By this time, long since the age of the dinosaurs, Earth would have grown, as a grape on a vine, and yet calmed. However, inside is a churning dynamo, and the overall composition of the planet was alike to today with only a few major changes visually and chemically. However, the marked quick changes in the electro-gravity environment would have meant powerful inertial, geological, radioactive, and climactic forces would suddenly emerge, driving people in fear, into shelter in reverent awe of the invisible power. Mankind, having no understanding of electromagnetism or of plasma discharge, may have witnessed these events in the sky and been both terrified, and ultimately inspired. To see God strike down vast swaths of animals with “Thunderbolts” would have inspired both fear and ambition. However, it certainly would have also convinced early man of the necessity for survival, and to borrow upon such a power as a religion.

This too, when such electromagnetic forces attract and repel, given that EMF is 10^{39} times stronger than gravity, the Earth’s crust would have made groaning, even trumpeting noises that would be echoed throughout the sky. Later on in history (and even to this day), such sounds are heard and inspire fear and reverence from hearers, globally.⁴³

Given these ‘portents’ and ominous changes, followed by precipitous climatic changes, it would be no wonder that mankind eventually would feel that their reverence, or lack thereof, would be the source of the anger and raw power. This subjective phenomenon is due to the tendency of the human mind and ego towards solipsism. When the mind is quiet, and therefore reverent, it naturally feels the center of attention - all attention. This is probably the result of evolutionary adaptation (if not Creative Design), for survival and heightened awareness. Studies of REM cycles show that people are in survival mode even while asleep.⁴⁴

⁴² Before Mount Olympus, the Titans ruled from Mount Othrys. The change in name suggests a change in plasma shape source. This will be covered further in.

⁴³ <https://www.insideedition.com/media/videos/source-behind-mystery-sound-heard-around-world-40074>
<https://nypost.com/2017/11/23/nobody-can-explain-loud-booms-heard-worldwide/>
<https://www.elitereaders.com/eerie-noise-heard-from-different-parts-of-the-world-explained-by-nasa/>

⁴⁴ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK11121/>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3317042/>

Is it little wonder, then, that later Flood myths from more than 100 cultures all reported the causes of the deluges were due to 'evil men' and/or 'evil animals' (megafauna)?

Imagine, therefore, the stimulating effect upon early hominids and homo-sapiens (biologically modern but not consciously so) to experience such wonders? The stimulation of belief, fear, and a driving need to survive. To become tougher, meaner, stronger, walk upright even, and of course, develop Intelligence as a survival mechanism. Language would be necessary (but not yet writing) as a matter of organization, of course.

Meanwhile the "examples of Heaven" would become made available. The angels and spirits suddenly visible in the sky, where before there may have been not much more than we have now in terms of large planetoids or moons and a central star. However, at that time, this star would have been central to us, and the Pole Star would have been that which dominated our entire view and thought. Indeed, it will have put out mostly a light red light, and lit a purple sky, while green would have been much weaker (and therefore plants would have repelled green as they do today and grown better in red light, Sol putting out mostly green light).

Imagine the power, too, if the transistor effect of electric stars ever came into play, if for example the approaching Ra/Helios syphoned away some of the charge of the binary system early, and the star began to flare or dim. At some point, of course the dwarfs did cease to attain a high enough core voltage to remain 'lit' and it is well known that "Apollo grew" in brightness and in size. But if this had happened earlier on as well, would not there have been cause for even more wonder at the "workings of Heaven?"

Another remark must needs be made about the end of the protective plasma sheath (giving way to Sol's dominant plasma sheath): the revelation of the stars, and of the Milky Way galaxy. The emergence of Heaven as a place, and of the entire pantheon of the planets, simultaneously with the fall of the outer plasma sheath. Mankind would have been inspired to evolve consciously, and prodigiously. In other words, religion would take an active and important role in early mankind as the source of scientific, technological, socio-political, and even economic⁴⁵ organization. It would not be religion as we understand it, but it would be a religion by any clear understanding of the word.

By the end of the first phase there would be plenty of roots laid in all departments, and it goes without saying that there could be expected a similar bell curve of IQ as per any modern society, although intelligence had not yet been gathered for full use. A case in point is the atlatl. It goes without saying that a spear is a natural extension of a knife and stave. Or that a bow and arrow represents a massive leap forward in weapons technology. However, the atlatl is an inspired weapon of some genius. It has range akin to the sling, but the advantage of still providing a hand to hand combat (melee) weapon as a spear. Such versatility is assuredly the invention of some unknowable genius of far antiquity.

The next phase, moving from small hunter gatherer groups into organized pre-civilized societies, perhaps even villages for the purposes of building these mounds and early pyramids is not well understood. The archaeological science has, hitherto, been actively thwarted by the mainstream and even governments. This has caused us to remain without answers as to how mankind went from caves to making the Bosnian "pyramids" with astronomical calculations built in, including also their proto-concrete, and how this phase would

⁴⁵ The exchange of resources, including perhaps mates or children, and a general bartering system; or even an understood set of rules of engagement as regards raiding (near to watering holes or other 'public' domains; possibly kill sites) would constitute a form of early commerce, if commerce is defined as the unified exchange of energetic goods.

be connected with Sundaland construction 12,000 years later, or Giza construction 12,000 years after that⁴⁶ leading up to the Younger Dryas Event (YDE).

The YDE marked the end of this great second phase, and it destroyed most of the evidence of its existence when it sank entire continents and islands. However, what remained was also purposefully dismantled or abandoned by the remotely antiquarian peoples, who were reduced to dire means of survival and clearly felt that this destruction had hailed the anger of God(s). It is presumable that they had some foreknowledge of the destruction from both the

The arrival of a massive foreign object into the Earth system was notable for three reasons.

1) The destruction of “Tiamat’s lover” (our first moon) led directly to the remnants of the asteroid belt and can date for us (relatively speaking) at least how long Sol has been in our solar system (at least 9-12kya). It also provides a visceral glimpse into the destructive power of the gods to end life.

2) The object, being closer than any other object had thus far come, caused widespread destruction, on par with that of the ending of the dinosaurs. However, the event was clearly electromagnetic (with some super-hurricane force winds) because the extinctions that resulted were too selective for a comet or volcano, and too widespread to be so selective, yet too global to be neither (invoking both as part of the mechanism of destruction). It needed to hail a mechanism for both causing the Younger Dryas - probably orbital alteration - mini Ice Age and how it would be ended. The current YDE “comet” hypothesis fails to explain itself as either the start or the end, and for the end, how to melt away all of the ice. Yet we know it must have melted, and in a hurry. Surely there must have been some electromagnetic event, perhaps Thunderbolts or something as simple as an electrically driven orbital change.⁴⁷ Based upon testimony, we know such event occurred in the Historic and Ancient Periods. By extension if the passage of celestial bodies near to Earth caused widespread electromagnetic catastrophes, it would also have in previous motions of the celestial bodies.

3) It is finally notable because it gives us the answers to strange behaviors and aspects about the moon, and the origins of the myths of the two-faced gods (Janus, Anu, Vishnu). The power of these destructive gods have left their mark even to this day in the form of popular media, calendrical and holiday reminders (January), and in many other little ways. But it also indicates part of the reason for lunar/tidal impact on human mood or psychiatric and criminal behaviors. There is a charge differential that remains in place, and although the moon is no longer close enough to Earth to break the permittivity of free space, it remains tidally locked such that one face always remains towards us and menaces us. The stories of our “Watcher” (sent by Enlil/Jupiter) has haunted us ever since. Our drive to go forward and verify for our own eyes that the moon is a benign rock (after which we collectively sighed and moved on) is understandable, as is the near religious fervor of the “space race.” In our quest to vanquish our enemies and drive our fears out, we embarked in one century to conquer the electromagnetic force, then space, and we even made a movie about the destruction of the “Death Star.” Although the Death Star is clearly more of a reference to Venus, as she (Athena-Medusa-Hela) was the

⁴⁶ The author understands mainstream resistance to the Schoch theory of erosion around the Sphinx, and to the Bauval “Orion Theory”; but the author maintains the evidence is strong overall that the Great Pyramids were not built during the First Dynasty but inherited from a far older culture, and were remnants “of the Gods.” As they have no inscriptions of believable value and represent a higher technology than that possessed in the First Dynasty, it goes without saying that the Great Pyramid(s) were an Atlantean-esque product, from a greater antiquity than Khufu/Cheops. They are, in fact, a series of improvements upon early power plant technology based upon the observations of the sky and early research into piezoelectricity, resonance, plasma discharge, and advanced chemistry. The evidence for the production and industrialization is contained in other works (see Appendix).

⁴⁷ The amount of charge in a body will determine its relative force of attraction to a star, and its natural repulsion by the stellar wind around the star, and the magnetosphere dynamics will create a “orbital shell” of sorts. Once Sol, for example, established its dominance in the solar system and syphoned off most of the plasma from the binary dwarfs (Saturn and Jupiter) it is obvious to see why the planets were “put in their place” in the same way that Jupiter thus controlled the planet Venus (Zeus sent away Athena), which was then taken up by the sun (Sol) and has since then become cowed in its random movements. Its rotation is now even slowing down.

cause of the Exodus catastrophe, and is known as the Morning and Evening Star, clearly the moon remains part of that equation. It is lamentable to say, however, that the moon is not yet safely only ours and will never both humanity again, although it seems less likely with each passing year.

At the end of the YD period mankind received its lift from probation (Enlil had installed the Moon "Watcher"). Temporary culture rebuilding resumed, and Zep Tepi came once more, this time in the Near East in upper Turkey/Armenia as the Tepe Period. Here, the "Eden" blossomed. That is to say, agriculture and endless food, wine, and beer.

It is no surprise, then, that when such a period was marked by a savage and severe end("the Clash of the Titan") mankind felt rather deprived. In Egypt the flooding worsened and the return of the Atlanteans was cut short, presumably by the original Deluge. The mythic evidence from the period is scant, and no language is found between Gobekli Tepe and Sumer to give us any indication as to why mankind retreated to within the Earth 9000 years ago and remained there for thousands of years, or above ground in squalor. The remnants of the Atlanteans buried Gobekli Tepe and its knowledge, and nothing of the sort re-emerged from all the chaos until 5500 years ago in the nearby but slightly southern Fertile Crescent: Mesopotamia.

What was the state of religion at this point? Greek Myth seems apt to give us some hint as to the behaviors of the planets and the state of relationship between humanity and the gods. First Cronus overthrew Uranus, and this was the first "falling of the sky" (the plasma sheath), but then Zeus overthrows Cronus. Here we see that Jupiter overtakes Saturn as our god-sun, although it is already no longer a brown dwarf. As the two split, Atum-Ra "recedes into the background" and Osiris rises (with Isis) into prominence. Set (the early sun) then battles with Osiris for dominance. But for the Greeks and Sumerians, Zeus-Enlil is simply disinterested in humans. Whereas Cronus ate his children (collisions of moons with Saturn), Zeus fornicates with them, or breeds new half gods. Sometimes he destroys humanity; sometimes he saves it. The moodiness of Odin is oft forgotten in later tales, but in the early ones his behavior as Enlil is compared and contrasted with that of the archetypal God of War (Marduk). In warlike cultures they are worshipped as father and son (such as Odin and Thor). But in Sumer and India, the memories are bitter, hate-filled and widely destructive. Entire cities are vaporized or burned away as God's messengers come to Earth to smite evil humans or followers of Marduk. Thus we see typical Othring in play from city-state to city-state, as different groups are encouraged by a vicarious survival to try harder and harder to appease the gods but also not choose wrongly. After all, Jupiter has many moons, and the position of Earth in this new pantheon (of the Aesir) must have been very precarious.

The gods reigned from a new Mountain (Olympus), and this mountain may not have been named until the passage of Mars close to Earth. However, the vault of Heaven, with its many zodiacal titans of the past, the former gods (receded gas giants and moons), giants, and angels etc... vie for power. In Peru ancient Paracans record the strange zoo of therianthropes while in MesoAmerica the gods are remembered for their animal like appearance. It was at this time that the shaman and the oracle rose in power equal to that of the astronomer. Why? Why would the religious leader of strange occult power be honored alongside the scientist who surely had more useful means of prediction relying upon calculations and records, and the obvious evidence provided by astronomical evidence?

For two reasons, ostensibly. On the one hand, in most cultures worldwide they were the same person (and thus the origin of wisdom traditions and wizardry and sorcery in general, and all the schools of magic). On the other hand the gods were fickle, and unpredictable. Although the Atlantean period saw a rise in astronomical prowess and machining and various industrial advances, even naval advances that yielded raw data in the form of the Earth's dimensions and degrees, the Archaic Period through right up until the roots of the Scientific Period saw a return to a flat Earth model which although had great interest in the Divine, did not understand it totally. The superstitious was embraced alongside the scientific. Look, for example at the death cults of Egypt, which inherited some textual evidences from Atlantean (pre-Deluge) sources, but in the end understood little but the cycle of death. They could not return the power plants to on, nor recall the making of glass Crookes

Tubes for lighting, nor how even the pyramids were made, truly. All attempts were clearly sub-par, and got steadily worse. After the Exodus cataclysm and the sacking of Egypt by the Amalekites it is doubtful even that any major attempt was made, except for the collection of the library at Alexandria, which was surely burned for religious superstition and not as an accident of war.

So in this Archaic period there are gods, but we don't understand them. Much as humanity tried, even personifying them and making long (incredibly long) songs such as the Rig Veda and the Mahabharata), or wrote about them in hieroglyphics that seem to us strange (even for a religion of death), the simple facts of astronomical power and Truth evaded mankind.

Blood sacrifice was, of course, tried. It did not, ultimately appease the gods anymore than fruit. Sumerians tried, at various times of drought and famine, to even starve the gods and approbate their deities. Countless societies fed their enemies and what they deemed as "unbelievers" to their own god, especially Marduk/Mars/Ares (indeed, in the zodiac of Aries)⁴⁸ who was of course, blood red in appearance, and near to us right back to antiquity and who would play a part in the epoch of Aries in usurping Zeus/Enlil/Odin. This "battle" was seen, naturally, as a continuation in the change of the line of kings. Kingship itself was derived, as was the belief in Divine Kingship and the Right to Rule via sword and by force, from this relationship between Jupiter and Mars (whom Jupiter had also taken from Saturn in the Clash of the Titans of the Archaic Age). It is unclear how many passes these gods (moons, planetoids, planets) and giants and titans and angels made towards the Earth, but orbits can have been as often as every few years or decades to hundreds of years apart.

The jobs of shamans and oracles to divine the Divine was of equal importance to the job of astrologers to predict and read the moods of the gods themselves, and speak on their behalf. If the professions had not met and merged in a culture, even as sophisticated as India or China, they would soon vie for political power and prowess. In India a priest class, nobility class, and military class (as opposed to everyone else) was created to define sphere of power because this order was seen as both protective and Natural - even supernatural-matching that of Heaven, after all. And it was presumed to be a workable solution to mankind's precarious survival.

Thus it was that when Venus/Athena arose and came forth in a blaze of glory it was easily seen as a good thing. At first seen as a male bull (plasma formations due to the passage of Venus through Jupiter or Saturn) and then as a warrior goddess, the Great Comet Venus brought awe, fear, and horror - as well as disease and pestilence, and plagues - to the world. The world was ready for another transition. The epoch of Aries was drawing to a close.

It's at this juncture, before we speak of the epic battle of Athena with Ares (Loki with Thor)⁴⁹, and before we speak of the interpretive differences that cultures have about this battle, and of course before we speak of the end of the age of the gods and rise of the One God (the sun, Shamash/Helios/Apollo) that we speak about the emergence of the messiah phenomenon; that we speak of what we can infer, but not necessarily know.

The first appearance of the messianic tradition was actually in Egypt, around the beginning of the epoch of Aries, at the end of Taurus. It is probable that the origin was the downfall of a Osirian cult, and of the defeat of Osiris by Set. What is unclear, though is if this means Jupiter (Enlil) overthrowing Saturn (Enki) (the archetypal slaying of a brother, as per Cain and Abel), or the movement of Mars in front of Jupiter, and the end of

⁴⁸ The Age of Taurus (the Heavenly Bull) was cut short by the Archetypal Hero (Gilgamesh or Thor) and ushered in the Age of Aries. The homonym of the sign Aries and of the Roman god Ares (Mars, aka Marduk) is not coincidental!

⁴⁹ In Greek tradition, Athena defeats Ares three times before she is sent away by Zeus. In the Norse tradition, which comes later, and owing to the worship of the archetypal warrior (who could not lose to the half male/half female brother Loki, a trickster god), Loki is instead defeated by Thor and banished by Odin for slaying Balder (another warrior); and the commencement of Ragnarok would come when Loki rises up once again (as Hela, whom he begat/transformed into) and the Midgard Serpent (Greek Typhon) returns to swallow the World Tree, and Surtur will wield the Twilight Sword once again (surely a Thunderbolt akin to Neptune's trident). Interestingly enough, in Mesopotamia Venus-Ishtar first sleeps with him, mating with him, but is later remembered in the epic of Gilgamesh as having been rebuffed by Gilgamesh and therefore earning him her ire and scorn, especially for the killing of the Bull of Heaven.

Enlil-Enki's rule, and Marduk taking control (Marduk is the child of Enki)⁵⁰. However, it is clear that through the story Osiris is meant to revive and come back as Horus (the son). The assumption being that Horus (Egypt's Gilgamesh, Greece's Hercules) is a demi-god as Mars is much smaller than Jupiter (the father).

So if the story is that Horus must vanquish Set (Sol, the sun), then why? And what connection did this have for humanity?

This is the part where myth and history begin to spin around each other, and generate each other.

Remember that the change of the age to Aries, ending (prematurely) the father's age (Taurus, the bull of Heaven) occurred prior to the emergence of the revenging Athena. It could be said that, perhaps as the son-warrior had not vanquished the sun (Sol) by the time of her emergence, that Zeus thought her into existence. Chances are that a previous planetoid, probably that which had hitherto been known as Hera or Metis crashed into Jupiter and passed through. Its origin, however, may have been new, and come from Ra/Saturn.⁵¹ It is not known.⁵² What is known is that this warrior goddess was first considered male and a bull, and heralded the Lord Enlil-Zeus. What is also known is that the savior did NOT come in time to stop Hela/Kali/Medusa from reigning destruction upon mankind midway through the Epoch of Aries, and indeed it was the power of the All-Father (Odin/Zeus) that sent her away to cease her from destroying mankind. So within a short enough period what was heralded as a good portent became terrifying, and what was terrifying then became horrific in the extreme, as any readings of Exodus will leave no doubt. The very power and might of God was invoked to explain these terrors, and it forced the issue of the many gods to contend with the new, emergent One God (Set previously, or Apollo, grown into full power, bright, and no longer dark). It caused the overthrow even before the Hellenistic Age and the Epoch of Pisces, when religion as we know it truly emerged as a powerhouse in all of human life all the way up until the time of the Hebrews and the struggles to deal with being both "God's chosen people" and also punished by God, and sent into a starving desert (laid upon the Earth as punishments). For many years, this struggle defined humanity, and refined the idea of a Savior (from women's 'impurity' and the stain of loss of the warrior god, etc...) and it naturally established itself in the human psyche as indelibly as the theistic traditions. Around the world the need and yearning for a messiah, to cleanse sins and end the punishment continued, unabated, until individuals began to fulfill the many prophecies (either via chance or true supernatural conditions or attainments). This age was then merged with the deistic-noble classes and priesthoods into modern religion. Many currents that had many roots merged in many places into a similarly reflected need: the need for Religion as we know it.

What is the innermost need within the human psyche for such a savior or messiah? It is perhaps related to the dabble into and growth of the cyclical belief in developing intelligence. In certain traditions, such as Taoism or Gnosticism, there is a persistent belief that unless you are like a stupified child, like an innocent, you will not be at peace. In Rosicrucianism there is even the belief that knowledge is the source of suffering. This is quite opposite to the Vedic belief that ignorance (dukkha) is the source of suffering, and yet there is something to it. In Genesis there is direct reference to the consumption of the forbidden fruit, which is not named, as it is in the

⁵⁰ The orbital tilt of Mars and Earth is still closest to that of Saturn. Earth has lost more of the Saturnian tilt due to being larger and descending faster. Recently Earth lost another ½ degree of tilt and the climate change effects have been remarkable.

⁵¹ An entire book may be, and has been, written of the age of Ra-Cronus, that is Saturn as our God. Let it be known, however that the emergence of the "Eye" of Horus or of Ra, emerged obviously *after* the end of the brown dwarf period, and the emergence of Saturn's rings, which are made of water and could not have possibly existed around a star. The "opening and closing" of the "eye" is clearly the optical effect of rotating around Jupiter, seeing God's eye in rotation and it appearing to open and close. It could not have been when we were in the World Axis as the orbit would be too stable.

⁵² The patronage of Loki is a confusing matter. In some myths he is accounted as a half-brother, and some as a step-brother, and coming from the Vanir, which explains his half femaleness, as the Vanir of Vanaheim (the Saturnian moons) are fertility related. However, it is clear that the Norse considered his tricky behavior as female, and not of a True Man. The Norse were replete with many machismo related laws in the feudal ages, such as the right to kill a man for calling him female or homosexual. <https://norse-mythology.org/tales/the-aesir-vanir-war/>

Gilgamesh, but is said to have come from the Tree of Knowledge of Good and Evil. This dichotomy is endorsed by repeated Taoist and Buddhist traditions as the source of “bad” whether in terms of health or spirituality. This is quite different than the rise of Satanesque belief systems where a Dark Lord (Set, Mara, Lucifer) who has “fallen” is the source of evil, and even gets within the person. However, the two currents seem to collide within the late Hellenistic Period, and as the era goes on, hundreds of schools of thought, philosophy, and the roots of many religions emerge with solutions and messiahs. Some promise the merging with the Atman or Bhagavan, some with the redemption in a beyond, or entrance into a Heaven or Nirvana. It is clear, therefore, that far from an Eden, Earthly life for humans had become a chore, and no longer a dream but even, at times, a total nightmare.

It is with this backdrop that one can appreciate both the diversity of belief/solutions offered **and** how the world, in emulating the gods became quite confused and entrapped in a technological race that offered solutions. But these solutions always created more problems, and yet mankind was unable to go backwards (for a fear and terror chases us from the past, and not even amnesia has enabled us to escape the horror).

Imagine then, the power of seeing the gods’ own Thunderbolts revisited to Earth. Not since the cataclysms of hurricane, volcano, up and down thrust of mountain and land, and of course deluges (multiple) had the wrath of the gods revisited mankind. Now there emerged a pair of gods which fought with the same power Zeus had used to vanquish Typhon. Moreover that power came near to Earth, bringing plague after plague, and worst of all the terrific Plague of Darkness. The world was even moved from orbit and the atmosphere struggled to keep with it. The sky “fell” a second time, and when it returned it did so with terrifying winds, and with the power unknown since the destructive end of the Tepe period. Whatever tidal deluges had occurred, wiping away the evidence of the past were nothing as compared to the horrors of the Younger Dryas culturally.

As children of the Religious Period would have grown up with fairy tales and religious invocations as warnings for moral behaviors, children of the Ancient Period would have grown up with tales of monsters and gods, the end of the world - multiple times over - in fire, water, wind, and rock. Stories such as in Lot, where his wife is turned to a pillar of ash, would have been commonplace belief. Transmogrification into therianthrope titan-esque monsters would have been invoked as religious calls for common sense morality. Law, as useful as it was, was clearly not effective enough. The [assumed] misdeeds of the Hebrew people, discovered by Moshe upon his return from one of the active angry mountains of fire (where a Thunderbolt had caused it to melt and smoke), gave power of the priest over the common herd; power enough to drive them both to safety and yet, into further ignorance and superstition. Only once that generation had died off was “proper” ritualistic tradition enabled and the religion brought about that brought Jerusalem into economic glory and wisdom.

So what was this great Exodus cataclysm⁵³ like? It was, of course, first seen as a breakdown of the Great Conjunction. Then, the planet Venus passed near to Mars and the period of star shapes began as plasma streamers passed from Mars to the backdrop Venus.

From there the situation worsened. When the distance between them extended, the familiar “bowling ball pin” like shapes of the Egyptian headdress and the “serpent” shape of a coiled snake consuming an egg appeared. This hailed the beginning of the terror. For once Venus broke free, it then passed in and out of the orbits in an elliptical manner, as a comet. The planet, as aforementioned, went through another planet, probably Jupiter, given the myth of Athena emerging from Jupiter’s forehead, and turned into a blaze of fiery green glory. The “horns” and “beard” she wore also appeared to some cultures as a dragon or tail devouring serpent.

As astronomers tried desperately to predict her movement, Athena proved herself the equal of old Hercules/Gilgamesh. She must have had many encounters with planetary bodies. But it was the electrical interactions with Mars, on multiple occasions that stupefied mankind. Some called it “mating” for the planets appeared to copulate with brilliant plasma energy. But to most cultures it was a stupendous battle. In India the

⁵³ Circa 1600 BCE; as per “Ages of Chaos” & “Worlds in Collision”, by Velikovsky

story is recounted in the heroic myths of the monkey man-god Hanuman (Sun Wukong in China) who helped defeat the demon king Ravana. This battle with evil clearly personifies something that is beyond humanity to help people to cope with the outcome. It is unclear from this myth which planet is the monkey king, and which is the demon king. But given the events of Exodus felt worldwide (such as torrential rains in China), it is clear that whichever planet passed near would be seen as evil or a persecutor, as Set returned. It is no wonder, then, that worldwide the myth of a Dark Lord emerged, and not only in Egypt. By the time of the Religious Period, most religions, if not all, had a personification of darkness, death, disease, and a personal persecutor which would torment the good, and impose evil will, and corrupt the hearts of people, causing them to turn, as Athena did into a Medusa, or as Mars did later, into a “scar-faced tyrant” (Thor becoming over-run with the “Warrior Madness”/Berserker rage).

Some time must be spent, it would seem, upon a related topic: the development of secular aspects of humanity. Religions are, as explained, survival systems, no different in some ways than militias or farming co-operatives. The exception is the reliance upon superstition and fear as motivations for morality (and cohesion that is brought from successful family structures and breeding - protection of ‘our group’), and of promise for eternal glory. Actually, in many cultures the latter could be had by the military class. Such as in Norse tradition whilst most people went to a form of Hades or Hell (meaning “to cover”), warriors went to Valhalla. Thus there was a separate path to the Heavens glimpsed oh-so-peacefully above at night (Milky Way and stars). But in general, only religion offered a means of total control socio-politically and spiritually. The military and nobility, oft combined into a knight class in many cultures, lived in need of the religious class for legitimacy and power right up until the Scientific Period. It was the religious class which developed most of mankind’s knowledge and intelligence, while it was the military class that developed its technologies and drove the need for political commercial advantage (barter naturally led to trade disputes). Therefore, the common class utilized and was utilized for legitimacy in maintaining the delicate balance of power. In Egypt if the power strayed too far to one side or another, the very next plague or famine would be blamed upon ineptitude. This happened also in Mayan politics. In China it was used as a rallying cry - the “Will of Heaven” was a stamp of approval for death and destruction, especially of enemy families and biologically successful lineages. This is, of course, natural and is seen in even lions and common mammals. When one bloodline becomes too powerful naturally others ally to overtake them.

The difference, however, is that religion offered an “uber authority” or mandate for the overthrow. In the case of the Greek Gods, this was personified in the son overthrowing the father. However, in the case of Athena, the female now exceeded the male (by defeating Ares/Thor). This could not be allowed to happen, and thus the rise of religion was simultaneous with an oppression of the female sex. This would have been mutually agreed upon amongst women and men, and in many cultures, especially in Asia, women have for many centuries valued sons over daughters. The mother goddess of the Archaic and long forgotten periods, of the Eden-like past, was lost and replaced with a distorted view of female nature.

Is it no surprise, then, that when in 600-700 BCE Mars passed near to Earth, Mars was suddenly feminized in India as the destruction goddess Kali? Her tongue of red dust descended (following the electric field) and laid a thick layer of destruction throughout the world, even covering massive areas with the sands of Mars, and pelting mankind with “thundereggs” which can still be found to this day. When the “Morning” and “Evening” Star (Venus) had, with her horns and beard, dropped ‘ambrosia’⁵⁴ upon the Earth (as we passed through her elliptical tail, mankind had revered the cow. Indeed in Egypt and in India the worship of the Bull from the age of Taurus was extended into a cult of bovine worship. Even in India, when bulls or cows go on a rampage to this

⁵⁴ The discovery of the hydrocarbon atmosphere of Venus is one of the great confirmations as to the nature of the ‘heaven’ of Heaven, mana/ambrosia. Hydrocarbons rained down upon the ground in places in great heaps of white milk-like substance that was able to feed people after starvation had reduced them to dire straits. It was seen as an act of love from Heaven and interpreted as a gift of the Mother Goddess. Figures of her divine breasts, which referred both to Venus and to the toroid of plasma discharge around the planet, are demonstrated by Dave Talbott’s concept of archetypes.

day, they are legally protected from slaughter. In Spain the running of the bulls remains a form of respect for this past foregone event.

The destructions, both from arc discharge and from the darkness of the plasma tail's dust (and diseases caused thereby), only ceased when Zeus-Enki vanquished the planet and sent it into orbit around the sun. Apollo, ultimately was the savior. It is therefore also no surprise that with the emergence of the bright son that there be also a dramatic rise in demand for a worship of a single God alone.

Whatever change in the electromagnetic fields between planets, it must have been powerful enough to break Earth free from Jovian orbit. However, before this could happen there was one more major cataclysm which would visit the entire world: the scar-faced tyrant Mars⁵⁵.

The destruction it wrought was not nearly as terrifying as that during Exodus. However, this scar faced 'god' was not seen as a true downfall of men, so much as the continuing corruption of a Dark Lord. In nordic tradition it is not Thor who is corrupt but Loki or Malekith-like "two faced" character.⁵⁶

It was not long, perhaps 20-80 years or so, before Mars and Earth also reached tidal phase lock as Earth had with Venus (and still has), and they were flung away from each other. This could have happened on the way from Jupiter towards Sol, or perhaps was the end of Zeus' power altogether. Certainly it wasn't long before characters like Socrates were expressing doubt of the gods' existences at all; or at least their importance. The beginning of a Hellenistic Period was not to commence around the world equally, but only in pockets we now call "civilization."⁵⁷

In Greece, China and India, hundreds of years of incessant warfare emerged, diametrically opposed by hundreds of years of religious and philosophical sages. Some of whom trained the political and military class in the technologies of thought and wisdom (such as Mozi, Sunzi and Aristotle). Some of whom refused to participate, such as Buddha and Zhuangzi.

What is clear about this period of time is that the transition from Archaic knowledge into Religious knowledge was one of the most important periods of adaptation of humanity for survival that has ever been witnessed. Because the war and strife and bloodlust was so extreme, religion was more important than ever in the conquering of violence and establishment of social and familiar order. Texts such as the Huainanzi, or the Torah, or the Sutras emerged as not simple guides nor mere laws, but confluences of knowledge that should not be questioned, nor should they be given to the masses. Instead, the noble and military classes became, in a way, subservient to religion for the power it held over all. This may have been profitable, or detrimental. In feudal systems it was largely profitable but forestalled scientific and technological advances unless they were in military, until the Age of Exploration. In imperial or monarchical systems it was definitely enriching culturally, but even more so hampered scientific advancement as the religious power was melded into a superstructure. However wisdom, in general, was more venerated in such systems, as it conferred natural advantages in political and military power.

In the end, however, religion did not prove itself (or has yet to), particularly with regards to the messianic prophecies, or promises of Heaven. Albeit one may or may not get to Heaven on account of proper conduct, proper life, reduction of karma, or via salvation or enlightenment: it has not as yet saved mankind from the two

⁵⁵ A direct reference to the Valles Marineris, and proof that early man had witnessed Mars in the sky up close, and had seen the destruction Venus had caused to Mars/Ares/Thor.

⁵⁶ The two-faced aspect of Mars is formed in a similar way to the moon's arc discharging and two faced hemispheres. However the difference is the northern hemisphere is much more completely machined and vast "shield volcanoes" were left behind, which are not found on the Moon (they were left on Earth in formations like Devil's Tower). This indicates not only the intensity of the arc discharge between Venus and Mars but the prolonged period of contact that would have been occurring during the Conjunction (collinear alignment) phase. For more information on collinear polar configuration see:

<https://arxiv.org/abs/1706.06204>

<http://www00.unibg.it/dati/persona/636/412.pdf>

<http://www00.unibg.it/dati/persona/636/413.pdf>

⁵⁷ The so-called "cradles of civilization," as we know it.

behaviors which most threaten our survival in the Scientific Period. First is the remaining desire to attain the powers of the gods, for warfare and destruction of enemies (and therefore the delusion of the Other, and Othering in general). Second is our blatant disregard for the cycle of life, and belief in nihilistic or dionysian behaviors. It is important to remember that Dionysus was not an original god. He emerged after the relaxation of the controls of the polytheistic ritualists, after they ceded their control over the masses when the gods departed. Nihilism clearly remains a natural extension of teenage angst, generated by a general sense or general lack of sense of purpose, which is now felt in modern people all over where wisdom traditions fail or go extinct. In societies where true wisdom died out (such as Egypt, or the Middle East), war and the wisdom of military classes (such as Samurai) kept youth, especially young men, busy with a form of purpose (and therefore social control and protection against self-destructive behaviors not found in most animistic societies) that directed energy into social behaviors. This is a system that remains to this day, as the United States Military engages in both worldwide domination and worldwide philanthropy. However, that is but a ratio of youth, and the remainder are left to deal with the possibilities of true nihilistic belief, should the lack of outer proof lead to doubt of inner need for a faith and a Divine Plan or Purpose.

For some, therefore, it is no surprise that the Scientific Period has offered exciting new religious devotions.⁵⁸ What began as earnest technological advances and seeking of solutions to mankind's problems quickly filled the superstitious minds of early scientists with promises of technological and "enlightened" utopias. Massive numbers of utopian and separatist religions emerged simultaneous to the advances of science. By the 1900s, science was beginning to become a religion all to itself. It had a history, a dogma, a ritualistic following, a ritualistic class, and had adopted many of the naturally successful institutions of religion, such as colleges and universities, a priest class (professors), and even forms of messiahs, such as Einstein or Tesla. With the advance of war into a mega-class, involving even the nuclear power of atoms (recently re-discovered from the Greek age), and the growing technocracy led by the promises of the energetic power and force of electromagnetism, it would not be shocking, therefore, to point to a change in the masses into highly educated yet superstitious and zealous believers. To be a superstition, all that remains is that the public not understand how it works, only that it does, and to maintain any ritual or dogma attached to the preservation of this knowledge. The Internet has provided this very means. However, as displayed with the atomic model, advancements and intelligence can come with a price: in this case the ability to question the dogma, for the sake of mutual survival.

Because of the nature of consciousness, and of generational decline and the need to re-educate each generation, Science can not only degrade in quality (if the principles degrade) and become confused with technology, but every individual and every social generation can become more or less trapped within a shell of consciousness.

To illustrate the point, consider the difference in belief structures even within the Scientific Period, even within the 20th century. Those who were born at or near the birth of the 1900s witnessed the electric bulb, radio, automobile, airplane, nuclear, and genetic revolutions, the widespread destruction of two world wars, multiple revolutions and a Great Depression, as well as the rise of television with the simultaneous decline of the nuclear family and traditional family values. However optimistic they were about the promises of Science and invention, they remained firmly interested in mechanical devices, such as trains, automobiles, and architectural construction. Dam and bridge projects, as well as the skyscraper revolution were everywhere. This, even amongst liberals, was a highly fiscally driven and conservative viewpoint: anti-communist, anti-homosexual, pro-nationalist, and anti-immigrant. The religious views of this time period can be stated, at least in the West, to be highly polarized towards tradition. Too much changing too fast, and there was a steep difference of opinion between Science and traditional religious views. In some parts of Asia, they were still revolting against feudalism and imperialism.

⁵⁸ Big Bang, Black Holes, Dark Matter, Dark energy, General Relativity/Einstein, Darwinian evolution, Computers/Internet, Television, Celebrities, etc...

Contrast this with the second half of the 20th century. The rise of technology meant greater and greater separation of generations from fundamental Science and math, a decline in test scores, and a rise in liberalized values, which meant an end to traditional family structures and religious routines. But as the technocracy strengthened, it demanded some form of framework, liberalized but rigid. The rise of peer-reviewed journals, and celebrity scientists with cooky theories that originated as marginalized ideas but devoted followers, usually atheists or agnostics who needed another Infinite Source (or sources, in the case of multiverse theory and string theories; the new polytheism) of infinite, unexplained energy, to form a modern cosmology for a Modern Period.

However, scientific evidence, thanks to a handful of men who remained dedicated to the Scientific Method, and to traditional research, continued to advance as well. The difficulty is in presenting such theories to a public which has accepted a media-controlled (or even strangled) dogma of Scientism which relies mostly on consensus, popularity, and politics rather than purely observed fact to make its way and change heads and hearts.⁵⁹

The role of religion, therefore, continues - as it ever has - to provide succor, or indeed numbing, to a public in amnesia whilst also supporting a war-driven technocracy, somewhat bent on a twisted (distorted) and inherited but degraded version of a messianic story. Behind both of which remains the unanswered riddle of the One God, the many gods, and the mysterious power (now identified and almost immediately cast aside: electromagnetism) they wielded that so definitively altered and shaped human consciousness. Religions previously also provided political, fiscal, and familial structures that aided mankind in survival, but in all three of which Scientism provides little assistance or even generates monstrous weapons that do great damage on one side of the planet or to one class of people, while bolstering the opposite (ignoring therefore the scientific understandings of both polarity and causality, as we have thus known it.)

Furthermore, the situation is worse than explained, from a religious and scientific perspective. From a scientific point of view, all equations require balancing, and yet the majority of technological sciences, such as geoengineering or chemical mining, or nuclear medicine, etc... have considered only the positive variables. The adage that the side effects of the medications are the effects of the poison and the side effect that it does anything positive at all, truly illustrates the dangers of purely optimistic and profit-driven motive in science. The dark art of finance and litigation economics correlates with the similar degrade in engineering to 'planned obsolescence' and reflects the downside of a capitalistic motive force in scientific pursuits, which encourages a degrade in morality as well as ethics and therefore real Science.⁶⁰ Science was designed to help humanity and improve human lives and hopefully in the future, the environments we live in which are now understood in all sciences to be crucial to human survival, happiness, and success.

From a religious perspective, much of what transpires to this very minute in the scientific community involves much that belongs to the realms of black magic, dark arts, or pure metaphysics. The latter is perhaps only regrettable as to the violence of which wasted resources and careers does to a society, especially when occasional results are funneled into military pursuits. The former represents dangers as diverse as moral and ethical violations of animal and human rights, environmental damage, etc... up to an exceeding genocide and even extinction level powers. Though black holes and wormholes may not be real⁶¹, the pursuit of them via particle accelerators funded by billions of dollars regardless of the "known" dangers surely represents the

⁵⁹ Consider the scientific research of Velikovsky, Arp, Birkeland, Juergens, and many others that was met with dangerous opposition bordering upon fascist or gestapo-esque: including spying, conspiracy, book burning, and coercion rather than simple presentation of fact. Rare victories against such methods did occur, but decreasingly so as the 20th century progressed. Although Alfvén did win the Nobel Prize, he lamented his magnetohydrodynamics and the concept of "frozen-in" magnetic fields, and tried to keep people from using it. However the dogmatic scientific community favored only what could give them a magical answer, and ignored his pleas. Since then they have even taken to calling it "Alfvén Reconnection."

⁶⁰ Science etymology: <https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/science>

⁶¹ Literally undefined and without merit or basis of fact. Also, not found in any close examination of the reported evidence.

results of distorted logic and reason, and a misapplication of the scientific method in the extreme. Other such dangers include but are not limited to: the formation of chimeras and therianthropes, nano-chemical weapons, geoen지니어ing such as spraying salt iodides into the air, and more. Due to the lack of a remaining fear of the gods and their judgments, and prescribed ritualistic daily living (behaviors between male and female, between sovereign and subject, in church, etc...) mankind feels more or less pleased to do with his time and resources as is pleasurable; and yet pleasure and passion (pain) go hand in hand. Ignorance and knowledge are both roots of suffering, and the three are miserable company, interlocked, much as are Fate, Chaos, and Karma.

It is beyond the scope of this paper to delve into this topic and the religious beliefs of Scientism. Certainly to wax philosophic too deeply about the nature of black magic study and the limits of ethics in scientific laboratory practices (with animal research or stem cell research, for example) would be pedantic in the extreme and miss the point. The main gist of the thesis here provided is that religious behaviors, including energetics, alchemy, and magic remain as potent as ever but in a new period of human survival and biological warfare. For indeed as surely as mankind has made warfare upon each other in remembrance and emulation of the gods and particularly Venus and Mars (our archetypal oppressor and warrior, respectively), so surely can we unmake them?

How far has humanity come in the psychological understanding of the issue will be deeply discussed in part two below. However, consider that 5,000-4,000 years ago, Sumer and India created a Star Wars of mythic gods and beings, and the Iliad and Odyssey, too were written over 3,000 years ago. These gods destroyed each other routinely with terrible violence.⁶² Entire cities, such as Sodom and Gomorrah, or Dwarka were destroyed (and some of these have been found). Herds of people, such as the Amalekites, Semites, Sea Peoples, Mycenaeans, etc... wandered about from place to place seeking new sources of food, water, and minerals and used warfare as well. To this day, mankind still views such events in awe, dealing with the tropes and hidden psychological meanings by spending massive untold amounts of money⁶³ on end of the world stories, myths, and destruction tales. Star Wars has in it two dark lords, and the murder of children, the explosion of a Death Star whose plasma beams could destroy a green and blue planet of peace, and there is too the mysterious unidentified Force that keeps all life alive. A not too dissimilar story also made a big splash recently: Avatar. The themes of religion, family, self and other, technocracy and warfare, connection, life-forces, and Nature - especially Mother Nature - remained central to the success of that story.

In the next part, the validation and problems of this model on the origins of religion (and religification of Science) will be discussed with some more detail or elaboration. The following Table will make a direct comparison of certain assertions, especially the more absurd ones (from the amnesic or myopic perspective) and the hard evidence that is not addressed in any other cosmology science, such as Expansion theory, Accretion theory, Evolutionary theory, Relativity theory, Egyptology, etc...

⁶² Let us not forget that Cronus "ate" his own children from time to time (moons collided with Saturn). Is it any surprise that in Sumer during some of the worst of the destructions there were mothers who ate or sold their own children for food?

⁶³ As of writing, the "Star Wars" franchise has grossed over \$7.97 billion in ticket sales; this excludes: DVD/physical sales, toys, merchandise, the cost of making the movies, the sale from Lucas to Disney, the black market sales, comics and other non movie media, side reference induced sales, etc... Another mega blockbuster series, the "MCU" (Marvel) has made also many billions (\$14.812 <https://goo.gl/CGjonu> and <https://goo.gl/wfQNEf>) and hinges upon end of the world plots, villains (including Hela and Loki), and soon another plot, "Avengers: Infinity War," will be released in which a "Mad Titan" will end the Earth with "Infinity Stones" (magical energy sources). It could be said that this is the same basic plot of the "Harry Potter" franchise, and many other movies. There are entire end of the world genre movies, such as "2012" and "Independence Day" which deal with similarly themed issues. Even children's movies, such as "Fantasia" and "Hercules" retell the Greek and Roman myths of worldwide destruction and heroes that saved humanity (the Mars fallacy).

Part 2 - Analysis of the Model

Table 4 - Analyzing Absurdities

Assertion	Details	Evidence Offered
Saturn and Jupiter ⁶⁴ as Brown Dwarf Parent	The Liquid Metallic Hydrogen model expects non-hydrogen lattice exclusion and induced exfoliation; the Electric Sun/stellar model and plasma cosmology also provides a mechanism for individualization via double layering and plasma sheaths Precedence of tiny dwarf stars has recently been found, however the main issue is that energy is mass, and so most of the mass Saturn and Jupiter had previously is not there, due to drop in charge syphoned off to Sol/Apollo	SAFIRE Paper 1 Dr. Pierre-Marie Robitaille Ralph Juergens Donald Scott (book) (video) (paper) Wal Thornhill (video) (book) (Thunderbolts) Kristian Birkeland (Currents and Nebulae) Marklund Convection (paper) 1956 Terrella Experiments (paper) Nebulae (double layers) (z-pinch) (motors) Galaxies (coplanar rotation) ⁶⁵ (CDM Free) Galaxies "On a String" (Magellanic Cloud) Direct Current Measurement Halton Arp "Intrinsic Redshift" (last talk)
Formation not by Accretion	The accretion has never worked in either simulation or observation. ⁶⁶ In contrast, many exoplanets have been found by searching near to dwarf stars ⁶⁷ or main sequence stars, and not farther away where dust could theoretically accrete via [weak] gravity over billions of years. Rather, instead the multiple composition of our own solar system suggests a heterogeneous system. The sheer volume of satellites surrounding Jupiter and saturn argue against accretion and for exfoliation. That they have similar magnitudes of them, and even some with water, but all quite diverse, and many with observed electrical relationships, such as Io and Enceladus bolster not only the Electric Star hypothesis but exfoliation as planetoid genesis.	TRAPPIST-1 LMH Model of exfoliation Saturn's Rings made of water (tidal lock) Similarities of Earth with Titan and Europa Similarities of Venus and Mars showing scars of massive discharge and "oversized volcanoes" Venus' superhot, hydrocarbon atmosphere Venus (and Uranus) backwards rotation Venus' rotation slowing down Venus' comet tail Uranus' tilt and this (Sumerian Myth) Retrograde orbits Pluto's eccentric orbit The Asteroid Belt and Boli (Enuma Elish) Lack of evidence of "dirty snowballs" and an "Oort Cloud" Presence of strong solar "wind" ⁶⁸ Quasar Exfoliation (Arp theory) Failure of Dark Matter hypothesis Star dust disks reveal LePoint formations rather than accretion disks. (SPHERE)
Moon late arrival	The two faces of the moon reflect vastly	Eclipse Patterns

⁶⁴ It is well known for many decades that Jupiter is still, to this day, putting out more heat than it receives, defying standard gas giant models all by itself.

⁶⁵ https://youtu.be/KUqV_2sj92U and <http://science.sciencemag.org/content/359/6375/534.full>

⁶⁶ <https://www.space.com/2206-death-spiral-theorists-cant-solar-systems.html> Accretion in any working manner requires electromagnetism: <https://goo.gl/wSmxEV> and <https://goo.gl/b4s2bD>

⁶⁷ <https://astrobiology.nasa.gov/news/red-dwarf-stars-and-the-planets-around-them-2/>

⁶⁸ The Solar charged "wind" is of course not a wind at all, but accelerated ([up to 50% the speed of light](#)) elements and particles. On one recorded occasion the sun's transistor-like behavior was displayed when the [SW turned off for two days](#).

	<p>different histories from the standard model. Based upon Accretion, the moon should be uniformly impacted, like Mercury, however it has a massively arc machined “front” face, which always faces Earth. The rotation of the satellite precisely (no coincidence) matches that of the Earth, which cannot and would never happen in the Big Whack, due to angular momentum conservation. The chances of this precision are astronomically low by such a method. Over billions of years such a momentum issue would definitely worsen.</p> <p>Moreover the orbit of the Moon is not planar, nor is it even elliptical.</p>	<p>Moon face machining (matches Mars machining) Hi-res imagery shows close knit arc craters Oblique craters are relatively few while crater chains are common Changing direction crater chains are also common; even defying topography Moonquakes follow a non-standard behavior that is suggestive of hollowness. Angular momentum laws themselves should be consulted for issues of revolution. They are never dealt with over any period of time in discussion of the Big Whack but completely ignored. Myths from certain tribes and cultures specifically mention the Moon as causing destruction worldwide, including the original Tiamat Myth in the Enuma Elish</p>
The Purple Dawn	<p>The sky was reported to be an indigo-purplish color. Meanwhile the current sky is blue due to the frequencies put out by the sun.</p> <p>This is contrary to the natural evolution of plants which should absorb green, if Sol was the original sun.</p>	<p>Qing (blue-green) is a common color phenomenon all over the world. Plants prefer red or blue light. even still it is used in hatcheries. The solar spectrum clearly shows an inordinate volume of green light in the visible spectrum, as opposed to red.</p>
The “Beginning” of Time	<p>Multiple cultures around the world report a “Beginning of the World” that occurred within human memory. It is referred to usually lasting only days. It is usually referred to happening after formation from chaos or the creation of light. This is directly contrary to geological evidence.</p>	<p>Zep Tepi and Egyptian records 36 kya “Dream Time” and Aboriginal Creation Myths Water clocks and off-angle but precise sundials (Worlds In Collision) Sudden emergence of clocks Calendrical problems not arising from bad mathematics.⁶⁹</p>
Change of tilt and/or orbital frequency	<p>Earth and Mars’ tilt axis preclude any possibility of accretion. The phase lock of Earth and Mars⁷⁰ to each other, as well as the orbital angles relative to the sun indicate a previous orbital ellipse path around the sun. Meanwhile myth, archaeology, oral traditions, and biological</p>	<p>Mammoth stomachs full of species too far north. Biblical and Chinese myths agree the planet’s North used to be its South⁷¹ The Piri Reis map shows a clear outline of Atlantis AND its rivers Astronomical correlations</p>

⁶⁹ It is remarkable that the scientific community feels mound builders, Egyptians, and Mayans (particularly Mayans) are so capable of creating incredibly precise calendar and even mechanisms, such as the antikythera mechanism, and yet are suddenly lax or imprecise with the most important values calculated for farming (and survival): equinoxes. Even the orders of the seasons are reported to have changed, and in sources ranging from the Bible to Chinese record we find reference to vast change in orbit of the sun (as viewed by the observer). This dichotomy, the author speaks of more length in the paper, “Plasma Petroglyphs, Geoglyphs, and the Megafauna Extinction.”

⁷⁰ Tidal or phase locking is a perfect example of electromagnetism overcoming newtonian gravity. Examples include: Earth Mars, Earth-Moon, Earth-Venus ([orbital resonance](#)), Pluto-Charon, and Saturn’s rings.

⁷¹ There appears to be a strange phenomenon currently where Chinese keep visiting Antarctica. <https://goo.gl/9YvSwP>

	evidence all suggest major changes to Earth's tilt and orbit.	
Lunar/Thunderbolt causes of megafauna extinction	The bulk of this is covered in the paper "Plasma Petroglyphs..." ³⁵ however, there is geological evidence as well as mythological evidence in the extreme that Thunderbolts were the cause of megafauna extinctions. The main argument for them is the overly selective yet unselective almost randomized nature of the extinctions, which has baffled scientists for an explanation. This vector is none other than Step Potential, which kills thousands of people and tens of thousands of animals every year. Only with plasma arc discharge of this magnitude it drastically altered the species populations globally, even where ice and humans had little to no impact on herd populations.	Delaware myth ⁷² Lakota myth ⁷³ MesoAmerican myths ⁷⁴ Biblical accounts ⁷⁵ Greek/Tridents ⁷⁶ & Typhon battles Zeus ⁷⁷ Sumerian and Indian Tridents Chinese myths ⁷⁸ Indian myths Norse Mammoths blown away where they stood Instant Petrification evidence ⁷⁹ Failure of Carolina Bay theories Barringer Crater and the missing impact fracturing ⁸⁰ Plus shape and depth issues. ⁸¹ Bullseye craters in Hudson Bay ⁸² South American Chibca and other Myths ⁸³ Devil's Tower ⁸⁴ Grand Canyon (a lichtenberg formation) Stone Mountain ⁸⁵ & Ayer's Rock (Uluru) ⁸⁶ The Knobs Region, KY (lichtenbergs)
Unrealism of Dark Matter/Energy	Dark Matter is actually plasma in "dark mode." Most of the missing matter has been found to be baryons ⁸⁷ , and the rest is un-needed to explain galactic alignment. Dark Energy is solely evidenced by a	Multi-charge CDM Search for electrons in CDM "Black hole" direct current measurement Baryon induced fluctuations in CDM Dark Matter missing in Galaxy Failure to find Neutrinos in CDM decay

⁷² "In Search of Ice Age Americans," K Tankersley, p 51-52

⁷³ "Cycle of Cosmic Catastrophes: How a Stone-Age Comet Changed the Course of the World," Firestone, West, and Smith

⁷⁴ Unfortunately most of the relevant Mayan and Aztec codices were burned (on purpose) in a single great fire July 12, 1562. For more info on Mayan myth see <http://www.mythencyclopedia.com/Le-Me/Mayan-Mythology.html>

⁷⁵ "He gave up their cattle also to the hail, and their flocks to hot thunderbolts" Psalms 78:48

⁷⁶ And <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Trident>

⁷⁷ Compare [Greek coin representation of thunderbolt](#) with [Zoroastrian Zervan](#)

⁷⁸ Most Chinese Myths refer to the later, Archaic and Transition Periods, and to humanity's survival. Such as that of Houyi. For more info, please see <https://thediplomat.com/2015/11/the-apocalypse-psyche-a-look-at-chinese-eschatology/>

⁷⁹ Google has suppressed searches for "Peter Mungo Jupp", the best continued research of this can be found on his website, [Ancient Destructions](#) or in this forum thread on Thunderbolts.info <https://goo.gl/tX4V7e>

⁸⁰ Strange to say, but the study is difficult to find, whereas numerous examples of shallow/surface seismic studying abound <here> <https://goo.gl/KDSVEs>, <here> <https://goo.gl/Vw3RAc>, and <here> <https://goo.gl/kMUeCB>

⁸¹ Note the square is not square but octagonal (see below); [the depth is also not conical. The fracture lines are very absent.](#)

⁸² Compare with well known impact sites, such as those in my presentation, or the [Chicxulub Crater](#). They lack bullseye rebounds of rim height altitudes.

⁸³ "Fingerprints of the Gods," G Hancock, p188

⁸⁴ http://www.sylvanrocks.com/devils_tower_climbing/legends_history

⁸⁵ [Stone Mountain is 825 ft tall](#), and this very much matches the KY Knobs lichtenbergs which never exceed 900 feet.

⁸⁶ [Wiki](#) <https://goo.gl/q2eWd2>, [Geology](#) <https://goo.gl/YArHDe>, [Myth](#) <https://goo.gl/3KWRq2>, [History](#) <https://goo.gl/juKr8Q>, [More Info](#) <https://goo.gl/EQSRUK>

⁸⁷ <https://www.newscientist.com/article/2149742-half-the-universes-missing-matter-has-just-been-finally-found/>

	misunderstanding of Red Shift. Halton Arp corrected this with Intrinsic Redshift, which means light not only slows down, but ages, ⁸⁸ as does everything else.	Dark Matter non-interactivity with matter Milky Way Halo not showing DM decay Halton Arp's papers on Intrinsic Redshift Birkeland Current Efficiency
Electro-gravity	The Structured Atom is able to accomodate for the weakness of the random nucleus model. Using Platonic Solids, it is able to accurately explain bonding and matter changes in a simple way that negates the need for neutrons and explains the nucleus' cohesion using a single unified force: electromagnetism (at close distances). Furthermore this approach explains the analogs of force/weight and gravity/lorentz force. Gravity is merely the resultant of differential of charge and distance	SAM website and new Periodic Table Electro-gravity (video) (diagram) (paper) The Weak and Strong Forces are actually just electromagnetism between quarks, bosons, baryons, etc... at very short distances . ⁸⁹ Note these are already measured in "electronVolts" Physicists eager to make up new matter, energy, and even forces Dinosaur and insect size limits ⁹⁰ Giants, gigantopithecus , and the decline of megafauna species ⁹¹
Expanding Earth	The expanding Earth is a secret of the USGS. Every year they set the GPS measured growth to 0 and pretend it is an error, however the actual number is closer to 140mm a year in diameter. It is common knowledge that the outer edges of the Atlantic coastlines fit, but few people know that the Pacific coasts and the Indian ocean coasts all fit as well.	Neal Adams Presentations SW Carrey Watch the evidence yourself More Explanations USGS report on growth changes ⁹² Professore Meyl explains neutrino induced growth (and this series) Tectonic Plates Shifting direction (paper 2) The potential Hollow Earth The potential water core ⁹³ How water is used to trap radiation ⁹⁴ The direction of radiation from Solar Wind entering at the Earth's poles Robert Distinti explains crustal collapse ⁹⁵
Origins of Tao,	Typhon, the Midgard Serpent, the plague	Earth in Upheaval and Ages in Chaos I & II

⁸⁸ "Tired light cosmology" is actually just part of EPEMC

<https://www.nature.com/news/cosmologist-claims-universe-may-not-be-expanding-1.13379>

⁸⁹ Note how much closer the other forces are to each other, while gravity remains inordinately weak. [Gravity Waves](#) are a concept [invented by Henri Poincare](#), and ultimately they are "bleed off" of charge ripples, which of course exhibit wave-particle duality.

http://www.science20.com/relativity_and_beyond_it/henri_poincare_predicted_the_existence_of_gravitational_waves_as_early_as_june_5_1905-165539

⁹⁰ One of the most horrific aspects of the Paleozoic Era and Triassic Period [is that arthropods](#) and [insects reached gigantic proportions](#). The fact that they do not anymore is a strong indication of gravity changes.

⁹¹ Not ironically, [humans still feel personally responsible for megafauna decline](#), despite the unlikelihood. The politicization of global warming and climate change has given rise to a false consensus about megafauna extinction. But kill sites found worldwide do not agree with the chronology or numbers. The fact that so many edible species remained later on casts doubts, not to mention the general population sparseness.

⁹² 0.00000038% or 8mm (radius) per annum. <http://subtleatomics.com/expanding-earth>

⁹³ In a future Whitepaper, the author will discuss the mechanisms that explain the heavy [EZ] water core and Expanding Earth, as well as crustal displacement and collapse.

⁹⁴ Exclusion Zone (EZ) Water: <https://www.pollacklab.org/> and Structured Water: <http://h3o2water.com/>

⁹⁵ Related discussion: Solar convection sources - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eTLVAuvT7e4>

Phaethon, Typhon, etc...	of Darkness, Hundun, etc... share in common a "genesis" of watery, chaotic, dusty, and deadly origins. In truth these events were occurring at the end of the Archaic Period and/or repeated during the Megalithic Period. As such, references to an origin in a black soup of chaos are common religious themes globally.	Taoism: Hundun ⁹⁶ Pangu ⁹⁷ Wuji Taijitu ⁹⁸ Norse myth & Jörmungandr ; Fenrir Zeus' battle with Typhon Phaethon Book Hamlet's Mill (audiobook) The Squatter Man/Great Man , and other plasma formations that are not planetoids but behave as titans . ⁹⁹
Electroquaking, geo storms, etc...	Weather is well known to be electrically related . The change in cyclone models includes now the understanding that cold wind actually drives tornados, not hot air, and there is no horizontal convection turned upright. Cold air carries static charge. ¹⁰⁰ But the more enlightened understanding comes from Earth Spots ¹⁰¹ : differentials in pressure and temperature, wind vector and intensity and upper atmospheric vortices that induce changes. When thermal energy is added to the equation then powerful vortices can occur. At the next level energy is affecting pressure buildup inside the lithosphere and crust, and a release can be triggered as an earthquake, volcanic eruption, etc... Such geomagnetic storms are related to magnetic tunneling from the sun, driven by Coronal Holes. ¹⁰²	Davidson (SuspiciousObservers) (paper) Weatherman's Guide to the Sun Electroquakes . ¹⁰³ Pakistan, October 8, 2005 China March 17, 2010 Indonesia April 11, 2012 Ionic Precursors M7.0+ Solar Polar Magnetic Aa Index Sept 2017 Solar Flare and hurricanes Triple hurricane event associated with flares SpaceNews Interview Magnetic tunnels Pecos Hank interview on formation of tornadoes

⁹⁶ "Hundun 混沌 was semantically extended from a mythic "primordial chaos; nebulous state of the universe before heaven and earth separated" to mean "unintelligible; chaotic; messy; mentally dense; innocent as a child"."

<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hundun>

⁹⁷ "Three main views describe the origin of the Pangu myth. The first is that the story is indigenous and was developed or transmitted through time to Xu Zheng. Senior Scholar Wei Juxian states that the Pangu story is derived from stories during the Western Zhou Dynasty. He cites the story of Zhong (重) and Li (黎) in the "Chuyu" section of the ancient classics Guoyu. In it, King Zhao of Chu asked Guanshefu (觀射父) a question: "What did the ancient classic "Zhou Shu" mean by the sentence that Zhong and Li caused the heaven and earth to disconnect from each other?" The "Zhou Shu" sentence he refers to is about an earlier person, Luu Xing, who converses with King Mu of Zhou. King Mu's reign is much earlier and dates to about 1001 to 946 BC. In their conversation, they discuss a "disconnection" between heaven and earth....

A brother and his sister became the only survivors of the prehistoric Deluge by crouching in a gourd that floated on water. The two got married afterwards, and a mass of flesh in the shape of a whetstone was born. They chopped it and the pieces turned into large crowds of people, who began to reproduce again. The couple were named 'Pan' and 'Gou' in the Zhuang ethnic language, which stand for whetstone and gourd respectively. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pangu>

⁹⁸ The swirl of the [original taiji \(yin+yang\)](#) indicate a similar perspective effect in the Venus/Mars separation from configuration as is demonstrated at the Great Serpent Mound. Twisting around each other is the long plasma streamers.

⁹⁹ <https://goo.gl/W8xBZn>

¹⁰⁰ The author's paper regarding electrostatic health effects is not yet released. However, [this graph demonstrates this](#).

¹⁰¹ <https://goo.gl/xzeKC8>

¹⁰² <http://www.weatherboy.com/exploring-coronal-holes/>

¹⁰³ Podcast discussion: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9XykMcZBolc>

The primary objection to this discourse, as was said in the Introduction, is that painting humanity with such wide brushes does take away a **lot** of detail of both variance and quality of analysis. In the end, there is no supercomputer in existence that can crunch the data analysis of all such civilizations. However, it should be possible (and necessary) to put together a rough timeline and turn what is currently blurred and fuzzy about the timeline of events into not only a reasonable chronology but even a “play by play” analysis of the astronomical events. The key is placing together seemingly unrelated bits of evidence.

For example, there is a Chinese aphorism, “Earth is square, Heaven is round.” In both the Amazon and the Ohio River Valley we also see the following similar formations¹⁰⁴:

Left: Newark Earthworks; Right: Amazon jungle
Credit: Newark Earthworks Park

Compare the strange (but clear and specific) octagon, with its multiple mounds at the corners, with this recently released infrared scan of the north pole of Jupiter-Zeus:

Credit: NASA/JPL-Caltech/SwRI/ASI/INAF/JIRAM (Juno Mission)¹⁰⁵

¹⁰⁴ For more religious symbolism explain via EPEMC, see Appendix B

¹⁰⁵ Each smaller vortex is approximately the size of the Earth.

Taken alone, such a comparison would be understandably written off as mere (very lucky) chance coincidence. However, this, plus the references to Mars being a “scar-face tyrant,” to Uranus being “hung by his heels,”¹⁰⁶ to the clear electrically driven formations of Devil’s Tower, Ayer’s rock, and Stone Mountain, GA, and to the names and numbers of the titans, gods, and giants themselves lends itself to a very easily understood system.

There are many ways to hypothesize about the Great Pyramid(s), however what is clear is they are modelled after something seen in the sky. The same thing can be said of the Nazca lines, the world’s earthworks, and of course the arrangement of constructions around the planet.

So what are we to make of these pieces of evidence? The mainstream archaeologists have, thus far, decided to ignore the cross connections and hide or deny the existence of certain out-of-place objects and evidence, content with descriptions of land bridges (though Clovis First has officially failed)¹⁰⁷ and instead keep to divided disciplines (such as Mayanology vs Egyptology vs Anthropology). This method may have been decent (this is debatable) for divide & conquer of the evidence in gathering it. But it is clearly insufficient for analyzing it. One might have different designers of different parts for a car (unlikely you would leave them to their own though with minimal specs or agreement), but one certainly wouldn’t have the car put together over two hundred years in a thousand different factories, and one most definitely would not expect the car to be aesthetic or even honest about its safety or performance.

Another objection that arises, naturally, is lack of evidence. This objection is summarily handled in two ways. First, to the charge it implies negligence, but it is only the unimaginative archaeological community which has failed to gather evidence or worse: to interpret the evidence and so conspire to hide it away. If anything, such as at Gunung Padang and Bosnia’s Pyramids, work is attempted and there is a clear effort to undermine progress. At places like Nevali Cori, the evidence is destroyed.¹⁰⁸ Or at Gobekli Tepe it is covered, harmed with concrete walkways, and prevented from further excavation. The recent finding of a void in the Great Pyramid illustrates the point well: they know the void is there, but they have no plan to excavate it (which in this case is fine because it will be empty)¹⁰⁹. In the case of Gunung Padang they know there is a chamber, but are unwilling to allow it to be opened up for both superstition and political reasons.¹¹⁰ Similarly, although Alan Wilson and Baram Blackett may have found the Ark of the Covenant in a deep scan of a non-ferrous box in a mound, by following the lines of evidence upon stele, the local archaeologists have prevented the excavation, and denied their work as fraudulent, despite all the evidence being made public.¹¹¹

The second way of dealing with the issue is the old adage, “Absence of evidence is not evidence of absence.” Troy was discovered buried beneath many feet of mud after so many thousands of years being buried. The archaeological community cried ‘foul’ at first, however eventually were forced to admit it was really Troy. This hasn’t helped correct British archaeology, however it has illustrated that the finding of places such as Troy, Dwarka, or Heracleion requires imagination. Not every site will be like Machu Picchu, just waiting to be walked upon. Or such as those in the jungles of Guatemala, waiting for LiDAR to reveal an extra few million people.

¹⁰⁶ References to an “Achilles’ Heel” exist in many forms. However, the myth in Sumer was of Inanna, ‘After she had crouched down and had her clothes removed, they were carried away. Then she made her sister Erec-ki-gala rise from her throne, and instead she sat on her throne. The [Anna](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Inanna), the seven judges, rendered their decision against her. They looked at her – it was the look of death. They spoke to her – it was the speech of anger. They shouted at her – it was the shout of heavy guilt. The afflicted woman was turned into a corpse. And the corpse was hung on a hook.’

<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Inanna>

For more information on the Uranus/Ouranus myths, see <https://goo.gl/gv1TsJ> and <https://goo.gl/GLvCHn>

¹⁰⁷ <https://goo.gl/Q4R39E>

¹⁰⁸ <http://bharatkalyan97.blogspot.com/2012/12/gobekli-tepe-and-nevali-cori-astronomy.html>

¹⁰⁹ All scientific evidence points to the room being an amplifier of the plasma signal in the nearby “vent”.

¹¹⁰ <https://grahamhancock.com/gunung-padang-latest-hancock/>

¹¹¹ <http://troedyrhiw-greenmeadow.blogspot.com/2009/11/discovery-of-ark-of-covenant.html>

Some will be buried beneath many feet of mud and dirt and clay. Some, it would seem, will be discovered by accident and be totally underground, such as at Nushabad.¹¹²

A final objection to the entire enterprise may be made by attempting to point at individual elements' "wrongness."

The author admits: much of the hypothesized model may be incorrect, factually, chronologically, and in interpretation. However, the model defends itself in two ways. The first by being the most up to date and comprehensive in both cascading point of view, and in application of Occam's Razor. What was requiring of many diverse and disjointed hypotheses is now explained in terms of reasonableness. No longer are religious studies able to ignore (or blame drugs for) the fact that the superstitions and supernatural events had to come from somewhere real or concrete to become a part of human evolution. Nor is the mainstream and public able to ignore (except via ignorance of the data) the very discussion of religious origins. Religion has become, in many ways, taboo to talk about (at more than the dinner table). It is yet vital to understand how the majority of the public is in fact still superstitious and quite believing in the supernatural. Despite the temptation to dismiss these things as predation upon an ignorant populace, there is need for scientific inquiry. Even subjects as diverse as ghosts¹¹³ and alien lights¹¹⁴ may be explained via EPEMC both historical-mythically and scientifically.

Indeed, the best rebuttal to all objections is that one must first collect as much data as possible and then begin to deduce what is possible from a total vantage point. The Talbott theory of applying "archetypes" to mythos and symbology makes logical sense. Only by studying the evolution of mythical archetypes which have had, hitherto no treatment and certainly no valid explanation, can we arrive at any truth about the past.¹¹⁵

There are, contrastingly, several profound reasons to begin researching this method in earnest, and to keep an open mind.

- The elimination of unscientific (pseudoscientific) hypotheses, which by definition can be neither proved *nor* disproved.
 - Ancient Alien or Alien Architect theory
 - Big Bang theory
 - Black Hole theory
 - Supersymmetry theory
- The application of Occam's Razor may yield new and exciting information that was not looked for in the past.
- The origins of religion and science, with hindsight, may provide wisdom and clues to our future.
- It may provide closure to the populace, and if there is an absence of evidence of current threat, we can apply vast wasted resources and potential to solving real dilemmas and crises.
- The end of warfare for resources (though for conflict of interest and ideals may continue).
- The exploration of space and new energy options and control of electromagnetism.
 - Charge Farming
 - Solar Wind and Asteroid Mining
 - Deep Space Travel

¹¹² <https://www.thesun.co.uk/news/3356728/samen-underground-city-iran-pictures/>

¹¹³ https://youtu.be/DJAmj1NxJ_w?t=27s

¹¹⁴ Such lights may have indeed been plasma electrical disturbances in the atmosphere due to cosmic rays. The recent discovery of "sprites" and other jets in the upper atmosphere, and of the Southern Lights has validated Birkeland's research into the aurora borealis and helped anthropologists to understand the Spirit World better. It may indeed have been true that there was far more "spirit" activity on the ground in the past than is today, during "Dreamtime." The recent first video proof of ball lightning has validated such strange phenomena fully. <https://goo.gl/bkCnBj>

¹¹⁵ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oEaUKe_gZUY and

http://www.thunderbolts.info/thunderblogs/archives/dtalbott08/051808_origins_of_myth.htm

- Faster than Light travel
 - Quantum computing
 - Quantum medicine and programming of cells
 - Removal of pollution
 - Terraforming Mars and Venus¹¹⁶
 - Moon Bases and cities for outpost and impact prevention
 - Ending droughts without chemical geoengineering.
 - Free Earth-resonant Power Plants (just like the Great Pyramids)
- The explanation of not only astronomical data, especially about the solar system, but an accurate interpretation of planetary movements, stellar genesis, and of course, mythical explanations become explained almost in full.

The application of the EP EMC can also, of course, be used to draw up reasonable objective comparison of religious systems (pros and cons), and to unite mankind not via legislation, not via warfare, not via subjugation of any sort, but via common ancestry, a shared story, and of course: a newer, improved religion that accounts for all the main facts while enabling spiritual interpretation. It would solve the conundrum of the One vs. Many gods, of the Messiah phenomena, and enable a proper interpretation of “Heaven” (Universe and energy and forces) and “Earth” (Matter within it), and of the Taiji (yin/yang) polar configuration and its many mysteries¹¹⁷ without threatening identities or causing cultural strife.

Yggdrasil: a motif preserved from oral tradition during Jovian time
 Nine Spheres/Realms + the Moon, verified by Chinese “Ten Suns”

¹¹⁶ From the evidence it would seem that Venus “stole” the atmosphere of Mars and this is why it is super dense. It probably also took its water through the arc-machining process.

¹¹⁷ Aside from electricity and magnetism, there is particle vs. wave, energy vs. matter, hot vs. cold, etc...

Conclusion

The Extended Plasma-electromagnetic Cosmology is meant to deal with topics ranging as broadly as diffusionism, catastrophism, astronomy, history, mythology, medicine, supernatural phenomena, and therefore also religion. Science today has become religious in its extrinsic display, and its adoption by a generally superstitious worldwide public. Therefore pseudoscientific claims and hypotheses have diluted the fields of science and prevented a rigorous application and investment of research into hard-based laboratory driven sciences, and consequently mired us in an inability to interpret past data and research to properly inform us for the future.

A course correction is being forced upon mankind by Nature, however amnesia or global ignorance has led to an arrogance based in past racial and spiritual trauma. Religions were born as a system of both survival and superstitious explanation of forces which were unseen and unknowable until the 20th century birthed plasma physics. This was so recent that only the invention of the Internet recently has enabled mankind to re-interpret this mythological and religious data to understand our impetus for warfare and billions or even trillions of dollars spent towards end of the world mythology (both past and present). Meanwhile crises that remain unabated grow.

EPEMC offers a fresh perspective on how to use this science and research to heal humanity and the planet's biospheres, prevent catastrophe, and bring mankind into the future: in religion, science, space travel, and environmental protection. Religion has been key to controlling human behavior and mitigating disaster and providing succor through survival situations, but has in the Scientific Period turned into a human hindrance.¹¹⁸

It is therefore vital that readers, leaders, and scientists review the evidence gathered, compare the successes and failures of the scientific community of progress, of religions, and of the technocracy itself, to make better judgments and forward mankind into a better future, devoid of obsessive paranoia about the past, and ignorant behavior about our present.

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The Great Man killing the animals with plasma streamer “thunderbolts of the gods”
Credit: Jean-Loic Le Quellec

Black Dragon Canyon, Utah

¹¹⁸ As Nikola Tesla would say, it has failed to advance Human Energy and Momentum. <https://goo.gl/bLfv0J>

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Appendix B - Religious Diagrams and Symbolism

Table 5 - Worldwide Symbols and Plasma-Electromagnetic Model explanations

<p>Vegvisir: all manner of peratt formations; Note the "Fire" (West) gua appears like a menorah</p>			
<p>Khakassia, Siberia: note the Peratt "tree" and the Celtic Cross, as well as the Squatter Man</p>			
<p>The Great Man: Kentucky; plasma torus clearly depicted (bottom) as well as pole? of Jupiter (Heaven)</p>			

¹¹⁹ https://youtu.be/n_l810EVYSU

¹²⁰ "Ancient Monuments of the Mississippi Valley". Squier & Davis

Mjolnir: trident from angle of Scandinavia, interpreted as hammer of Thor; associates trident with Thor / Mars / Ares

Valknut: symbol of death, associated with Odin /Jupiter/Baal; Suggested counterparts are Venus and Mercury or Mars

Triquetra: Suggested as symbol of mystical power passed from father to son: Bor>Odin>Thor Aka electromagnetism

Trident/Vajra: various thunderbolt shapes, would depend on angle of perspective and cultural adaptations.

"Alligator" Mound: note the 5 legs and trident formation; Adena culture, Ohio

"Turtle" glyph: note the 5 legs; Kentucky

Ouroboros: symbol of infinity and reincarnation. The actual path was elliptical however, some bodies (Moon) in our sky move as an analemma.

Ishtar¹²¹ (Mother Goddess); ruling on behalf of Shamash, Ishtar was enemies with Gilgamesh

Sumerian depiction of defeat of Dragon/ Monster (Greek Typhon)

Hadid /Baal : note the horns and vajra, and conical hats, Lebanon

Enlil / Zeus wielding thunderbolts, Sumer

Tawa (Sun Kachina): Planet Jupiter as Helios (the sun)

Nu'ut (Uranus) and Amon (Anu/Bor/Enki): depicting first beginning, possibly Milky Way, Egypt

Nu'ut: re-depicted under new religion, associated with wings. Two planets locked together become two Eyes of Horus. Egypt

"Face" glyph: shows same arrangement as above Nu'ut. Kentucky

Inanna with wings (see Nazca wings), tridents, and foot on lion. Akkad

¹²¹ [Ishtar \(Venus\): Innana. Aphrodite \(beauty form\). Athena \(warrior form\). Nu'ut & Isis](#)

Hunab Ku: symbol of balance Nican Tlaca, here we see the chaotic period ending as Liangyi (separation) leads to Taiji (great union)

Swastika: symbol of balance, life, and peace A worldwide sigh of relief as Venus moved away from Earth

Great Man depiction reaching from two-faced object towards another object; suggested from Moon towards Mars. Arc-debris noted clearly. Kentucky

Awen Symbol: subjection symbol of 3 powers in Heavens and plasma streamers

“Celtic” Cross¹²²: Symbol of Mars/Venus or Venus/Saturn/Jupiter conjunction

Same: Kentucky

Engraved relief: Mating phase depicted with moon Kentucky

Astronomy site: “owl” conjunction chiseled more recently, as compared to polar configuration; Awen symbol implicated. KY

Hand Glyph: contains monkey glyph; Aztec, Mexico

Great Man, Thunderbirds, and Great Wolf-dog; Nazca?

“Foot” glyph: the left foot or hand plasma shape; note material in center of foot clearly depicting activity. Kentucky

“Turkey foot” glyph: asymmetrical (altered perspective) awen depicting conjunction, Kentucky

¹²² Celtic is an inappropriate term for Welsh/Khumry and Pictish origins, however it is still standard.

Hill of Tara: Venus-Mars "mating" with plasma sheaths clearly seen, Ireland

Same: Kentucky rock art

Biggs Site Mounds (destroyed): clear depiction of conjunction of Helios, Venus, and Mars, Kentucky

Same: sketch of Biggs Site; note the conical mound formation, one of the best examples worldwide until destroyed Compare with Sumerian hats.

Cerne Abbas Hill Giant: masculinized version of Peratt formation; depicts the "owl eyes" as testicles, and the toroids/gua as ribs, and the planets Mars and Venus as nipples. Probably an amalgamation of oral histories to depict God/Squatter Man, England

Same figure, depicted upside down, from southern hemisphere; note it is also at a different phase, thus one arm up and one down. Nazca, Peru

Nazca Thunderbird: Note the shape of the feet The general asymmetry of these earthworks, lines, and glyphs is dealt with in the author's aforementioned paper, "Plasma Petroglyphs..." It is a perspective issue. Peru

Thunderbird glyph; note the Awen symbol in chest; depicts end of world scenario. Four toed "talons" reach down (thunderbolts). This is after the discharge of one; Kentucky

Mayan Thunderbird Concentric circles representing Jupiter and Saturn, for the Norse: Aesir and Vanir

Rock "Eagle" Mound: North American / Cherokee or Creek depiction of Thunderbirds, Georgia

Monkey Glyph: note the feet and spiral, and compare to above hand glyph of Aztec¹²³

Great Serpent Mound: world's largest effigy mound, built on top of Thunderbolt "bullseye" crater; depicts Venus "Great Comet"; note spiral tail is perspective leaving Mars. Ohio

¹²³ Note also the arms are in octagonal shape, and spiral is circular, and compare to Newark and Amazon.

New Nazca Lines: note the 5 legged animal and Thunderbird, Peru

Newark: Hopewell depictions of Heaven and plasma turned into a religious "campus", Ohio.

Amazon Earthworks

Keiki Beach Squatter Glyphs: even isolated until Modernity, Hawaiians from ancient times (and Haida in Canada) depict the same Peratt formations. Oahu

"Concentric circle" relief glyph: depicts planet inside center of polar view of either Saturn (or Jupiter), which have hexagonal poles¹²⁴. A very old motif according to wear, and meaning. Kentucky

Movement glyph: perhaps reference to gas giants and our quadrad¹²⁵ leaving the gods and dispersing. Kentucky

Dragon motif: same as serpent consuming itself = Jormungand, etc... Mayan

Kukulcan: Great dragon that devours the world; note the spiral motif and two spheres (compare to movement glyph at left); the movement of Venus into destroyer mode; Mayan

Great Man: short arm depicts angle has unique perspective as compared to Old World and Peruvian glyphs; Kentucky

Rock Art: from Conjunction to moon; Mars is in front of Venus, Ontario

Holy Cow glyph: combines the hand/foot motif with symbolism, possibly tells us the event occurred in the house of Taurus, indicating this is aged to Late and Middle Kingdom; Kentucky

Feet glyphs: show clear outlines of celestial bodies, Kentucky

¹²⁴ <https://www.sciencealert.com/saturn-s-mysterious-hexagon-has-changed-from-blue-to-gold-and-no-one-knows-why>

¹²⁵ Earth, Moon, Mars, and Venus

<p>Owl Glyph: depicts plasma sheath and conjunction; KY</p>	<p>Awen symbol shows clear asymmetry (subject of other paper); Kentucky</p>	<p>Mt. Horeb, Lexington, KY Mounds State Park, Indiana</p>	<p>Henge glyphs: depicting polar configuration; explains entrance mounds such as Mt. Horeb</p>
<p>Jupiter's South Pole: hexagonal, with counter-rotating cylinders in atmosphere¹²⁶</p>	<p>Jupiter's South Pole (color): Up to 15 layers thick plasma sheathing, as seen in SAFIRE paper 1.</p>	<p>Moon's Bull's Eye Crater: defies impact physics and shows clear discharges¹²⁷</p>	<p>Hexagonal Bull's Eye crater: impossible impact physics; Mimas</p>
<p>Eye of the Sahara: site of massive Mars to Earth discharge when Mars dumped the Sahara on Earth; Mauritania</p>	<p>Credit: Andrew Hall¹²⁸ Lightning made conical mound, formed by prolonged discharge. This is the anode. Southwest, United States</p>	<p>Concentric circle glyphs: with exit to side, and squatter man (and modified hands); shows clear meaning of cause of craters - the "Great Man";</p>	<p>Credit: Andrew Hall Maars of Pinacate¹²⁹: showing clear crater rim discharges, Sonora, Mexico (Properties of Shock Waves) (Electric volcanos) (Arc Blasted Mountains) (Torrential Winds)</p>

¹²⁶ Caused by solar system sized Birkeland "coaxial" currents. [Counter-rotation is expected](https://arxiv.org/pdf/1712.08414.pdf). See Donald Scott and JPL <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1712.08414.pdf>

¹²⁷ Both the Moon's bull's eye(s) and Mimas' famous one, as well as the millions more especially on Mars, account for the counter-rotational shape of a plasma Thunderbolt discharge. The hypothesis therefore being that seemingly random locations for heng mounds worldwide are not random at all. Earth was heaped up upon worn down craters to keep them viable as worship spaces. The entry-ways were rim discharge burns that wore away, **leaving a pathway into the henge**.

¹²⁸ <https://thedailyplasma.blog/category/electric-universe/page/2/>

¹²⁹ <https://www.thunderbolts.info/wp/2017/01/20/the-maars-of-pinacate-part-one/>

The Squatter Man: proof that the original conception of God was either alien, or more likely, a series of electrical discharged (a world's tree) connected to the radiating star, Ptah/Atum/Re/Kronus - the brown dwarf Saturn. Aboriginal Australia

Petroglyphs vs Plasmaglyphs
Combined geometry and familiar shapes, with coronal outlines indicate types of plasma sheaths and protective layers which are indicative of charged atmospheres. Could this be the Titans/angels? Dominican Republic

"Mantis" glyphs: could easily be mistaken for a predatory creature, however several of the glyphs reveal a secondary purpose. Compare with "centipede" glyph (KY) and the underlying Z-pinch stratification becomes obvious. The "eyes" are just more Venu/Mars conjunction Alcudia Valley

"Dream-time" (aka Zep Tepi in Egyptian): the time of the first sun. Clearly there was, at one point, a several layer plasma sheath. Compare with SAFIRE Phase 1:

Credit: SAFIRE Project

Sakwala Baswati "stargate": a smorgasbord of plasmaglyphs with the same central theme. The "pyramid shape" confirms that the idea for a pyramid or "mountain of Heaven" was visible in stars. This location is very ancient; Sri Lanka

"Rain-Man": clearly not a typical humanoid figure (note: head/trident and arms). The rain, or "hail" are thundereggs from Mars. Peru

"Viracocha": the Zeus figure of Bolivia. This site, Tiwanaku/Tiahuanaco, is of renowned age. The Venus/Mars conjunction or "Owl Eyes" is clearly visible with a backdrop of solar rays. Bolivia

"Dinwoody Site": what at first appears to be a grotesque bearded man is now obviously more conjunction and discharge. Wyoming

Lascaux Cave "art": the concept of art is new, but these go back 30,000 YBP. Could have been a record. Why is the bull so large? Is this from the Age of Taurus? France.

"The Great Man": something descended from the mating (or suckling); was it 'ambrosia'? Australia.

Faceless Squatter Man: the conjunctions went through many stages and phases/shapes. Here are several as seen from Sicily.

"Newspaper Rock", Utah

“Running Man” and Spratt Serpent Mound: sometimes made with stones instead of dirt, making it harder to date.
Frenchburg, KY

“Man on the Moon”: aka Janus or Anu. An ancient force of shaping and destruction, responsible for geological changes worldwide that “broke Tiamat in two.” The remains of electric arc machining are obvious comparing both faces of the moon.

“Jack-rabbit” glyph: lacks head and has added feet. Close observation shows distinct bass relief of two hurtling objects with plasma tails (not ears). Legend Rock, Wyoming

End of Great Conjunction = cause of cometary hail and forming of new mountains. Wyoming

“Tolar Petroglyph”: the menorah and descent of the 9 “stars” (that Houyi shot), the 10th remaining. The animal is interpreted as a horse **prior to** the return of horses to the area. Thus the plains’ Indians’ fixation on horses. Note the Great Man was seen above the back as in Kentucky, but here with greater detail. Notice the Nazca like lines. Sweetwater, Wyoming

“Corn glyph”: the American Indians saw the “tree of life” as corn, rather than a tree; other interpretations include the hand conjunction shape, a very clear concentric (plasma sheath) circle glyph, and the “Step Pyramid” shape, as well as the typical Awen and “8” style toroid. Wyoming

“Square Spirals”: Beaver Creek glyphs show a unique presentation of the spirals, more suggestive of the breakdown phase of the plasma sheaths: Compare again with SAFIRE phase 1:

Coastal Observatory: this is a strange location for preserving art and heritage, but a perfect (no tree cover) location for astronomical observations. This is also what is found in Ireland and Hawaii. The Canadian coastal Haida people pride themselves in their ancient origins; British Columbia. Each of the following four sites below will repeat this motif. Mainstream archaeology has no explanation or even an attempt for this phenomenon.

Helluland, Viking

Arizona

Loughcrew Eclipse Rock, Ireland

Etowah River, GA, USA

7 Pyramids found on the African Island of Mauritius.

Step Pyramids are generally agreed to be the work of ancient peoples. However, most people do not understand that they are not a Mexican phenomenon, but worldwide. Mauritius, Indian Ocean

“Tenerife Pyramids”: At first these were dismissed as later (imitation) creations, but Thor Heyerdahl has pointed to signs of extreme antiquity. Many have speculated they are the remnants of Atlantean Period peoples. The author here contests these are too new, but instead are from the same period as the conjunctions shown in the Wyoming glyphs. Canary Islands, Atlantic Ocean

“Chichen Itza”; Mayan step pyramids are widely regarded as the most important and best examples. Compare this quality with the well dated Egyptian Step Pyramid of Djoser:

Dated accurately to 4,100¹³⁰ YBP in the First Dynasty. This helps us to date the glyphs and other movements worldwide.

“Pyramid of the Sun”: Set in Mexico City (formerly Tenochtitlan), this amazing pyramid, the best of the movement, has been called an Aztec pyramid. It can now be laid to rest that indeed, the Pyramid of the Sun referred to the previous Sun, Shamash or Quetzalcoatl, which is the primeval sun (for this culture), which at the time was Jupiter/Jesus, unless it be, as usual, in remembrance of the First Age, and to Saturn.

“Monk’s Mound”; not the real name of the mound. The mysterious Cahokia people did build really large step pyramids, however they were the inheritors of an ancient mound building tradition. St. Louis, Missouri

“Poverty Point”: not the real name of this location, either. Note the original step pyramid. This site is currently dated up to 1700 BC. Considering the conjunction formation, and the shell shape, this location is probably just prior to the Exodus cataclysm (1600 BC).

Akhenaten worshipping Atum-Re: The fan-rays of the sun are associated with “shell glyphs” The headdress with the Mars/Venus conjunction.¹³¹

“Kofun” ‘keys’ mounds: These odd shaped step pyramids should not be misinterpreted to the same period or the same rays. They are newer, from the age of Mars’ descent, which caused red dust to stretch forth towards Earth. However, they may call back to the first time in design; Japan

¹³⁰ Subtracting the added 600 years Velikovsky discovered were added by erroneous early Egyptology. See “Ages of Chaos: Volume I”

¹³¹ This is a particularly important ceremony being depicted. At the end of the conjunction, Venus started to extend far out of phase, and create a long “bowling pin” shape of plasma. The shell shape of the glyphs meant that the gods were falling from the sky. In this context Akhenaten is praying to the two gods to return to position and re-establish the wonder days of Atum-Re, Zep Tepi. He is famous for failing and his movement towards archaic monotheism is overturned. The panic to appease the gods would have been very intense. Some have speculated, for many reasons he was the pharaoh of Exodus, and indeed may have even been Moses, although there is not much physical evidence to go on.

<https://grahamhancock.com/moses-akhenaten-same-person-osman/>

Adena Meadows, Red River Gorge, KY - A True Mystery
Credit: "KY From Above" (LiDAR)¹³²

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http://www.arcgis.com/home/webmap/viewer.html?url=http%3A%2F%2Fkyraster.ky.gov%2Farcgis%2Frest%2Fservices%2FElevationServices%2FKy_DEM_KYAPED_5FT_MultiDirectionalHillshade%2FImageServer&source=sd